

Accelerating the Transition to Sustainable Seafood Production in Europe's Seas

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Executive summary

Marine ecosystems are vital to Europe's biodiversity, food security, economic resilience, and societal well-being. Yet, these ecosystems face increasing pressures from human activities, including overfishing, habitat degradation, pollution, and climate change. These challenges not only threaten marine biodiversity but also undermine the long-term viability of industries such as fisheries and aquaculture, which many coastal communities throughout Europe rely on for their livelihoods.

EU policies, including the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), and initiatives under the European Green Deal (EGD) — such as the Farm to Fork Strategy and the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, including the Action Plan: Protecting and Restoring Marine Ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries — form the backbone of efforts to transition toward sustainable fisheries and aquaculture. These initiatives emphasise the need for ecosystem-based management, biodiversity conservation, and climate adaptation. However, gaps in implementation and enforcement continue to undermine their effectiveness in addressing the challenges facing Europe's seas.

This report examines these challenges through a comprehensive assessment of the impacts of fisheries and aquaculture on marine ecosystems, providing regional analyses and actionable solutions aligned with EU sustainability objectives.

Introduction sets out the context for the report, outlining the **policy landscape** and emphasising the need for action to accelerate the transition to sustainable fisheries and aquaculture in Europe's seas. It highlights how these efforts are critical to achieving EU environmental objectives and ensuring the long-term health and resilience of marine ecosystems.

Regional assessments introduces a **semi-quantitative risk-based framework** for a preliminary (first) assessment of the environmental impacts of fisheries and aquaculture activities across Europe's marine regions. Building on the ICES ecosystem overviews, it evaluates the direct pressures of EU fisheries and aquaculture subsectors in the Northeast Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea on key ecosystem components, providing actionable insights to guide policy and management. Data visualization tools, such as the Sankey diagrams, illustrate the relationships between activities, pressures, and ecosystem impacts, emphasising dominant drivers and affected components. This is an iterative framework and further work is needed (see Chapter 5).

Preliminary findings reveal:

- **Fisheries:** the primary pressure exerted by all fisheries subsectors is the extraction of living resources, mainly on fish species but also notably on cephalopods and elasmobranchs. Other notable pressures include physical abrasion, noise and marine litter. Vessels using active gear, particularly demersal trawlers, are the primary contributors.
- **Aquaculture:** pressures vary regionally. In the Northeast Atlantic, the main pressure is the extraction of living resources reflecting the reliance on fish meal for high trophic species. In the Mediterranean Sea, high trophic species farming in coastal areas impacts benthic habitats, while low trophic species farming adds to invasive species pressures. Other pressures, including nutrient enrichment, noise, siltation and marine litter, also differ in intensity across large regions while interactions with wild populations rank high in both regions.

Note: Sankey diagrams for fisheries (top) and aquaculture (bottom) in the Northeast Atlantic (left) and Mediterranean Sea (right)

Actionable solutions and mitigation measures to support sustainable fisheries and aquaculture identifies **actionable solutions** and **mitigation measures** to address overexploitation, habitat degradation, climate impacts and other critical challenges. These solutions are guided by transition objectives and supported by various monitoring programs designed to assess progress toward these objectives and targets.

For **fisheries**, these may include:

- **Science-based catch limits:** Implementing quotas based on robust stock assessments to maintain fish populations at sustainable levels.
- **Area-based management:** Establishing temporary fishing bans during spawning seasons and expanding and effectively managing MPAs to protect vulnerable habitats and species and to support sustainable fisheries.
- **Selective gear and technology:** Promoting gear innovations to minimise bycatch, reduce habitat damage and phase out harmful activities, complemented by AI-driven monitoring.

- **Combating illegal fishing:** Enhancing detection and enforcement mechanisms to prevent illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing.

For **aquaculture**, these may include:

- **Low-Impact practices:** Encouraging the adoption of environmentally friendly production methods and good management practices
- **More sustainable fish diets:** Developing alternative and diverse feed sources to lessen reliance on wild fish stocks.
- **Improving industry resilience to climate change:** Promoting innovative tools and technologies, species diversification and selective breeding, marine spatial plans to cope with climate change scenarios.
- **Regulatory streamlining:** Simplifying administrative processes to foster sustainable growth in the sector.

Towards assessing the performance of existing measures lays out the groundwork for assessing the **effectiveness of existing measures** for fisheries and aquaculture. While progress has been made in certain areas, such as reducing fishing pressure in the Northeast Atlantic, many measures remain insufficient. Key challenges include weak enforcement of existing regulations, such as the landing obligation and bycatch reduction, which hinder meaningful progress. Similarly, aquaculture regulations often lack the precision to address regional ecological and operational conditions. Closing these gaps and determining where measures should be scaled up or strengthened is critical to achieving sustainability objectives. This requires adopting integrated approaches, including:

- Incorporating high-resolution spatial data, evaluating cumulative impacts, and developing adaptive management frameworks to enhance the ability to respond to emerging challenges.
- Regional cooperation and harmonised policies for addressing transboundary issues such as pollution, habitat loss and climate impacts.
- Innovation and capacity-building to empower stakeholders to adopt sustainable practices.

Concluding remarks concludes with a forward-looking agenda for sustainable fisheries and aquaculture. To continue supporting and assessing progress on the transition to sustainable fisheries and aquaculture, future developments and improvements to the framework will explore regional and subregional specificities, by enhancing the spatial coverage, revising the impact scoring and incorporating uncertainty and confidence levels to improve the robustness of the scoring mechanism associated with each assessment.

By integrating scientific research, policy frameworks, and actionable solutions, this report outlines a path toward sustainable fisheries and aquaculture in Europe's seas. Achieving this transition will require coordinated efforts from policymakers, industry stakeholders, researchers, and local communities, with a shared commitment to protecting marine ecosystems and supporting sustainable livelihoods.

1 Introduction

Key messages

- 1. Climate change, pollution, overfishing, habitat degradation and biodiversity loss:** Human activities are placing increasing pressure on the marine environment, critically affecting ecosystem health and resilience. Overexploitation, bycatch, and habitat degradation remain key drivers of declining marine biodiversity.
- 2. EU strategies for sustainable fisheries and aquaculture sectors:** EU policies for fisheries and aquaculture are aligned with broader European Green Deal objectives, particularly through the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies. The Farm to Fork Strategy emphasizes the importance of sustainable blue foods, while the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), supported by the Fisheries and Oceans package—including the Marine Action Plan—promotes sustainable and resilient fisheries and aquaculture, contributing to the EU’s Biodiversity Strategy and the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**.
- 3. Strengthening EU policy implementation:** Although some progress has been achieved under the CFP, further efforts are necessary to reduce ecological impacts, achieve sustainable long-term yields, and build climate resilience. When managed effectively, aquaculture can contribute to sustainable food systems, enhance food security, and provide a reliable source of aquatic foods with a low environmental and carbon footprint, alleviating pressure on wild fish stocks.
- 4. Framework for Sustainable Fisheries and Aquaculture:** This report introduces a proof-of-concept for semi-quantitative analysis of the impacts of fisheries and aquaculture on the marine environment. Designed to assess and compare these activities regionally, the framework helps identify and mitigate their direct ecological impacts. It also explores potential short-term solutions and mitigation measures to address overexploitation in fisheries and promote responsible aquaculture practices.

Fisheries and aquaculture are vital sources of income, nutrition, food security, and well-being for many coastal communities across Europe. These sectors rely on the ocean’s renewable living resources, which in turn depend on healthy, clean, non-toxic, productive and resilient ecosystems. However, various human activities at sea—including maritime transport, offshore energy, coastal tourism, fishing and aquaculture — heavily impact marine biodiversity and ecosystems.

Overfishing, bycatch and habitat degradation are key drivers of declining marine biodiversity. Currently, around 40% of fish and shellfish populations in Europe’s seas are not in good biological status or are not being fished sustainably. Additionally, domestic EU fisheries and aquaculture production supplies only a minor share of the aquatic food consumed within the EU, with over 70% of seafood imported to meet the demand of the average EU consumer, who consumes approximately 24 kg of seafood annually ([EUMOFA, 2023](#)). At the same time, the fisheries and aquaculture sector faces growing competition for space and resources from other maritime activities, such as offshore wind farms. With over 93% of Europe’s marine areas already experiencing multiple pressures from human activity—including the impacts of climate change ([EEA, 2020](#)), the situation risks worsening as the blue economy expands, unless it is developed sustainably ([EEA, 2024](#)).

1.1 Policy context

The [EEA/EIONET Strategy 2021-2030](#) aims to enhance the support for the effective and coherent implementation of interconnected EU strategies under the **European Green Deal**. This includes key initiatives such as the Fit for 55 packages, the European Climate Law, the **Biodiversity Strategy**, the **Farm to Fork Strategy** (F2F), the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Zero Pollution Action Plan, among others. The F2F strategy sets out both regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives covering the whole food chain from production to consumption, with the common agricultural and fisheries policies providing support for a fair transition.

Habitat protection and restoration are the two main focuses of current efforts towards marine biodiversity conservation. In the EU context, a series of directives have been established for this purpose, including the Birds Directive (EC, 2009), the Habitats Directive (EC, 1992), the Water Framework Directive (WFD, EC, 2000) and the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive** (MSFD, EC, 2008).

The MSFD aims to maintain or achieve "*clean, healthy, productive and resilient*" marine ecosystems, while ensuring the sustainable use of marine resources. The MSFD requires Member States to take measures to achieve and maintain Good Environmental Status (GES) of the marine environment, which is determined at the level of the marine region or subregion based on 11 qualitative descriptors.

More recently, the **Nature Restoration Regulation** (EC, 2024b) sets binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems. Such regulations are also embedded in the recent EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy (in turn, aligned with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework) and the **EU Action Plan: Protecting and Restoring Marine Ecosystems for Sustainable and Resilient Fisheries** (EC, 2023b) that together aim to achieve the protection of 30% of the sea area, with at least 10% being strictly protected. These efforts collectively aim to ensure the sustainability and long-term resilience of marine ecosystems while aligning with broader EU environmental and climate goals.

The existing EU environmental legislation and the **Common Fisheries Policy** (CFP), together with national measures, should collectively contribute to minimising the risk of overexploitation and promote more sustainable fisheries and aquaculture sectors. However, most objectives remain to be met as, for example, [marine biodiversity is declining, not all fish stocks are exploited sustainably](#) and aquaculture has not achieved its potential as a sustainable source of protein to alleviate pressures on wild fish stocks ([ECA, 2023](#)) ([EEA, 2024](#)).

The Marine Action Plan, adopted in February 2023 by the European Commission as part of a comprehensive [Fisheries and Ocean package](#), also aims to support the EU Biodiversity Strategy and emphasises the need for sustainable and resilient fisheries. The plan outlines several critical actions, including:

- *Improving implementation, monitoring, and enforcement of regulations.*
- *Phasing out bottom-contacting gear from all Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) by 2030.*
- *Increasing fishing selectivity to reduce bycatch and discards.*
- *Protecting sensitive species and their habitats.*
- *Strengthening the knowledge base through enhanced research and innovation.*
- *Improving governance and stakeholder involvement.*
- *Promoting outreach and education initiatives.*
- *Supporting transitions through available funds, with assistance from the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)*

The Action Plan complements the [Energy Transition Initiative for the EU fisheries and aquaculture sector](#). Currently, these sectors remain heavily dependent on fossil fuels and are particularly vulnerable to energy crises ([Guillen et al., 2023](#)). Transitioning toward sustainable practices and alternative energy sources will

help reduce this dependency and support the European Green Deal's climate neutrality objectives. Key aspects of the initiative include:

- *Decarbonisation Plan: Increase energy efficiency and switch to renewable and low-carbon energy sources.*
- *Targets and Goals: Reduce fossil fuel use intensity by at least 15% from 2019 levels by 2030 and achieve a CO₂-neutral footprint by 2050.*
- *Research and Innovation: Develop technologies to reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.*
- *Stakeholder Involvement: Engage fishermen, producers, industry, NGOs, shipbuilders, equipment producers, researchers, and renewable energy providers through an energy transition partnership (ETP).*
- *Funding and Support: Secure financial support from the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), innovation fund, and Horizon 2020 programs.*
- *Skills Development: Ensure the workforce has the necessary skills for the energy transition.*

The sustainable development of aquaculture in the EU is one of the key objectives of the Common Fisheries Policy. In line with the CFP, the [Strategic Guidelines for EU Aquaculture](#) (2021-2030) align with the European Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy, focusing on 4 main objectives:

- *Building Resilience and Competitiveness: Enhance the sector's ability to withstand challenges.*
- *Participating in the Green Transition: Promote sustainable practices.*
- *Ensuring Social Acceptance and Consumer Information: Increase transparency and public trust.*
- *Increasing Knowledge and Innovation: Encourage research and technological advancements.*

The strategic guidelines identify 13 key areas where further work is needed to promote the sustainability, competitiveness and resilience of EU aquaculture: (1) Access to space and water; (2) Regulatory and administrative framework; (3) Animal health and public health; (4) Climate change adaptation and mitigation; (5) Producer and Market Organisations; (6) Control across the supply chain; (7) Diversification and adding value; (8) Environmental Performance; (9) Animal welfare; (10) Communicating on EU aquaculture; (11) Integration in local communities; (12) Data and monitoring and (13) Knowledge and innovation. The implementation of EU aquaculture guidelines is supported by the EU Aquaculture Assistant Mechanism, which will assist the Commission, member countries, and industry in the process by 2030. The Aquaculture Advisory Council (AAC) will also assist the EU Commission and Member States by informing and submitting recommendations and suggestions on matters relating to the management, socio-economic and conservation aspects of aquaculture.

1.2 State of play and report focus

The European Commission's recent communication '[Sustainable fishing in the EU: state of play and orientations for 2025](#)', provides an update on the state of EU fisheries and initiates a public consultation on the current situation and the future directions of fishing opportunities for 2025. After 11 years of implementation of the CFP since its 2013 reform, the 2024 assessment highlights several key results:

- The economic performance of the EU fishing fleet varies significantly across segments and regions, with fuel costs and the state of fish stocks being major influences.
- Fleet segments that rely on sustainably exploited stocks tend to be more resilient and offer higher wages to fishermen.
- Conversely, segments that depend on overexploited stocks and have higher fuel demands show weaker economic performance and lower salaries.
- In the Northeast Atlantic, stocks are now, on average, fished sustainably, though certain fisheries, such as cod and those in the Baltic Sea, face significant challenges.

- In the Mediterranean and Black Seas, while most stocks are still overfished, there is a positive trend toward reducing overfishing.
- Compliance and enforcement of the landing obligation remain generally weak, which affects the quality and reliability of scientific advice.

The European Parliament’s resolution on “[Striving for a sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture: the way forward](#)” (EC, 2022) acknowledges that EU aquaculture can provide healthy food with a smaller climate and environmental footprint compared to land-based agriculture and can play a role in achieving a carbon-neutral Europe by 2050. The resolution outlines the main obstacles to aquaculture growth within the Union and suggests potential solutions. It emphasises the importance of setting quantitative objectives for aquaculture development within the framework of existing guidelines — similar to targets established in the Biodiversity Strategy, Farm to Fork Strategy, and other Green Deal initiatives. Additionally, it calls for the establishment of environmental targets and regular monitoring to ensure compliance with the resolution’s recommendations.

Building on the ‘**Roadmap towards sustainable fisheries and aquaculture - A risk-based approach for the monitoring and assessment of cumulative impacts of pressures affecting EU seas**’ (ETC TP, 2023; Bastardie et al., 2024), this report advances efforts in monitoring and assessment to support the implementing of a sustainable blue food production system in Europe’s seas.

Specifically:

- **Regional assessments** presents a proof-of-concept framework for a semi-quantitative analysis that evaluates the impacts of fisheries and aquaculture activities on the marine environment at a regional level (North-East Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea).
- **Actionable solutions** and mitigation measures to support sustainable fisheries and aquaculture examines potential short-term actionable solutions and mitigation measures to address overexploitation in fisheries and promote sustainable aquaculture development in Europe’s seas, guided by main transition objectives and monitoring programmes designed to assess progress towards these targets.
- **Towards assessing** the performance of existing measures builds on the foundations laid in chapters 2 and 3, outlining the next steps for the continued development of this work, including assessing the performance of existing measures aimed at reducing the negative impacts of fisheries and aquaculture on Europe’s marine ecosystems.
- **Concluding remarks** concludes with a forward-looking perspective, highlighting areas for future research and methodological advancements. Future iterations will involve more detailed assessments, including analyses at sub-regional levels and improved metrics for evaluating the environmental performance of fisheries and aquaculture. As this framework evolves, it will provide increasingly refined insights and targeted solutions to support sustainable practices across Europe’s seas.

2 Regional assessments

Key messages

- 1. Framework for Regional Impact Analysis:** This report introduces an initial semi-quantitative framework to assess the regional impacts of various types of fisheries and aquaculture activities. By directly linking human pressures to their effects on key ecosystem components, this analysis offers critical insights for developing actionable solutions and mitigation measures to promote sustainable fisheries and aquaculture across the EU.
- 2. Key Findings on Fisheries Impacts:** Findings indicate that extraction of living resources is the primary pressure exerted by all fisheries sectors. In the **Northeast Atlantic**, the most significant impacts are on fish populations. Other notable pressures include abrasion and noise, particularly from large vessels using mobile bottom-contacting gear. In the **Mediterranean Sea**, impacts are more diverse, affecting fish, cephalopods, and other ecosystem components, reflecting the multispecies nature of regional fisheries. Additional pressures from fishing include physical abrasion, marine litter, and sediment siltation, with large vessels, particularly trawlers, as primary contributors.
- 3. Key Findings on Aquaculture Impacts:** In the **Northeast Atlantic**, aquaculture activities exert notable pressure on marine living resources, impacting fish populations, pelagic habitats, and food webs. In the **Mediterranean Sea**, high trophic species farming in coastal areas creates significant pressure on benthic habitats and wild populations, with invasive species pressures associated with low trophic species farming. Other pressures, such as nutrient enrichment, noise, siltation, and marine litter, show regional variations in their relative contributions.

Regional cooperation and assessments are essential for effectively managing the marine environment in the EU, as issues such as pollution, overfishing, and habitat degradation, are transboundary in nature. Collaborative efforts are essential to tackle these challenges and develop consensual, region-wide solutions. Regional cooperation helps establish harmonised policies and standards for marine protection, strengthens governance structures, and supports the enforcement of environmental laws and regulations. It also encourages stakeholder participation in decision-making processes, enhances monitoring efforts, and improves data sharing by setting standardized frameworks for data collection and dissemination.

In this report, we assess the impact of fisheries and aquaculture on the marine environments in the Northeast Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea. By categorising each sector into sub-components, we evaluate the direct pressures exerted by each and their relative impacts on various ecosystem components.

2.1 Overview of the EU's regional fisheries and aquaculture sectors

European fisheries are diverse and range from highly industrialised distant-water fisheries to small-scale artisanal fisheries that typically operate near the coast. EU citizens consume large quantities of seafood each year (currently around 24 kg on average per inhabitant per year in 2021; EUMOFA, 2023), and many coastal communities rely on fisheries and aquaculture for their livelihoods, well-being and food security.

Globally, aquaculture has emerged as a major source of seafood; however, in the EU, marine aquaculture production has not kept pace with these global trends, with capture fisheries continuing to dominate seafood production in the region (EC, 2022, STECF, 2023). The status of fish stocks in Europe's seas varies significantly by region. In the Northeast Atlantic Ocean, certain stocks are showing signs of recovery, leading to modest increases in capture fisheries' landings and improved economic performance (STECF, 2024). Conversely, the Mediterranean and Black Seas face more critical conditions, with fishing mortality rates above sustainable levels. However, the proportion of overfished stocks in these regions has dropped below 60% for the first time, continuing a declining trend that began a decade ago. Although overfishing remains a concern, the past year saw a 15% reduction in overfishing, aligning with an ongoing decrease in fishing pressure, which has declined by 31% since 2012 (FAO, 2023).

The following sections provide a concise overview of the EU fishing fleet's activity and aquaculture production in 2022, focusing on the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea regions. It highlights recent trends (compared to 2018) and differences across key fleet components, such as Small-Scale Fisheries (SSF) versus Large-Scale Fisheries (LSF), as well as gear types, including passive and demersal active gear, within these regions. Aquaculture production by country and main species groups are provided.

2.1.1 EU Fisheries

The EU fishing fleet operates across Europe's marine regions and beyond, with notable regional differences in fleet composition, fishing effort, energy use, and production levels. According to the 2024 Annual Economic Report (AER) on the EU Fishing Fleet, in 2022, the fleet comprised of 52 830 active vessels. The sector employed 119 702 fishermen, equivalent to 75 816 Full-Time Equivalents (FTEs), with an estimated average annual wage of EUR 30 273. That year, the fleet consumed 1.6 billion litres of fuel and spent 5.1 million days at sea, landing 3.49 million tonnes of seafood valued at EUR 6.6 billion, generating a gross profit of EUR 1.1 billion (EC-JRC-STECF, 2024).

Atlantic herring was the top species landed by weight in 2022, with 455 000 tonnes, followed by European sprat (348 163 tonnes), blue whiting (234 553 tonnes), skipjack tuna, Atlantic mackerel, and European pilchard. Skipjack tuna, valued at EUR 331 million, led in terms of landed value, followed by European hake, yellowfin tuna, Norway lobster, and European anchovy. Together, these six species represented nearly a quarter of the total landed value by EU vessels in 2022 (EC-JRC-STECF, 2024).

A regional analysis of EU fleet activity for 2022 (based on the AER methodology) indicates that fleet activity has declined since 2018, with an estimated 18% reduction in fishing days, a 19% decrease in landings by weight, and a 3% decrease in landed value across all regions (Table 2-1).

In 2022, the small-scale fleet (SSF) - defined here as all vessels under 12 metres LOA – experienced a 10% reduction in landings by weight and a 6% decrease in landed value compared to 2018. The large-scale fleet (LSF) – defined as all vessels over 12 metres LOA - saw a more significant 20% decrease in landings by weight and a 3% decline in value over the same period.

Table 2-1 EU fishing fleet activity in 2022 and recent trends by marine region and sub-region.

Region	Sub-region	scale	Fishing days			Energy use			landings in weight			Landings in value		
			(thousand days)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(million litres)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(thousand tonnes)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(million EUR)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total
Baltic Sea	Baltic Sea	SSF	240,3	-24%	5%	5,3	-32%	0%	34,4	-33%	1%	42	-21%	1%
		LSF	26,2	-38%	1%	40,5	-30%	3%	430,8	-31%	13%	120,7	-26%	2%
North-East Atlantic Ocean	Greater North Sea	SSF	71,3	-18%	1%	12,0	-13%	1%	23,4	-24%	1%	93,2	-13%	1%
		LSF	151,6	-9%	3%	311,4	-12%	20%	783,4	-27%	23%	1059,0	-8%	16%
	Celtic Seas	SSF	99,6	0%	2%	15,8	-30%	1%	105,7	23%	3%	148,0	25%	2%
		LSF	85,8	-10%	2%	185,9	-20%	12%	435,9	-23%	13%	686,7	-2%	10%
	Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast	SSF	634,6	-13%	13%	35,6	-15%	2%	66,8	-12%	2%	380,1	10%	6%
		LSF	238,2	-14%	5%	192,4	-15%	12%	366,1	-7%	11%	843,3	8%	13%
	Macaronesia	SSF	73,8	-7%	1%	4,1	-12%	0%	7,7	-21%	0%	42,2	14%	1%
		LSF	22,1	-6%	0%	14,7	-2%	1%	28,0	2%	1%	74,0	20%	1%
Mediterranean Sea	Western Mediterranean	SSF	620,9	-16%	12%	25,0	-18%	2%	22,7	-11%	1%	189,6	-13%	3%
		LSF	227,4	-29%	4%	135,3	-32%	8%	90,5	-30%	3%	492,2	-20%	7%
	Central Mediterranean	SSF	565,5	-32%	11%	14,0	-29%	1%	8,8	-33%	0%	73,6	-26%	1%
		LSF	84,2	-35%	2%	45,6	-54%	3%	20,8	-39%	1%	134,3	-40%	2%
	Adriatic Sea	SSF	476,7	16%	9%	15,3	-5%	1%	11,6	5%	0%	78,3	16%	1%
		LSF	205,3	-20%	4%	91,9	-42%	6%	124,8	-26%	4%	342,9	-18%	5%
	Eastern Mediterranean	SSF	960,1	-25%	19%	17,5	-25%	1%	11,3	-43%	0%	88,3	-47%	1%
		LSF	90,9	-13%	2%	39,5	-21%	2%	40,6	-2%	1%	129,5	-37%	2%
Black Sea	Black Sea	SSF	14,2	-20%	0%	0,6	-17%	0%	2,7	-51%	0%	3,4	-32%	0%
		LSF	7,1	-29%	0%	2,5	-15%	0%	6,1	-44%	0%	4,9	-32%	0%
Non-EU waters		SSF	95,5	-6%	2%	8,8	32%	1%	7,8	-7%	0%	57,2	17%	1%
		LSF	64,5	-4%	1%	382,9	3%	24%	798,9	-4%	23%	1543,2	22%	23%
EU fleet total		SSF	3852,6	-18%	76%	154,0	-18%	10%	302,8	-10%	9%	1196,3	-6%	18%
		LSF	1203,3	-19%	24%	1442,4	-18%	90%	3125,8	-20%	91%	5430,9	-3%	82%
		All	5055,9	-18%	100%	1596,5	-18%	100%	3428,5	-19%	100%	6627,2	-3%	100%

Data source: MS data submissions under the 2024 Fleet Economic data call (EC-JRC-STEFC, 2024); All monetary values adjusted for inflation; constant prices (2022).

Figure notes: (1) Results are estimates of the fishing activity by region/sub-region based on the data and regional analysis methodology developed and used in STECF AER reports; (2) regional and sub-regional totals may not add up to EU totals due to incomplete data submissions (e.g., missing spatial information for one or more variables; see 2024 AER Methodology for more details).

Northeast Atlantic EU fisheries

EU fishing activity in the Northeast Atlantic region contributes 53% of the EU's total landings by weight and 50% by value despite accounting for only 27% of the fishing days. However, it consumes a significant 48% of the total energy use. Since 2018, activity in the region has seen a 15% drop in energy consumption and a 20% reduction in landings by weight (Table 2-2).

- **SSF** dominates in vessel numbers, but its contribution to landings (11%) and energy use (9%) is modest. Since 2018, SSF saw a 12% reduction in fishing days and a 19% drop in energy consumption, while landings by weight remained stable (+1%) with a 9% increase in value.
- **LSF** makes up the bulk of the region's output—responsible for 91% of the energy used, 89% of landings by weight, and 80% of the value. The LSF has seen a 15% reduction in energy consumption and a significant 22% drop in landings by weight while remaining rather stable in value (-1%) since 2018.

- **Passive gear** account for 42% of fishing days but use only 15% of the energy, contributing 13% of landings by weight and 27% in value. While energy use has dropped by 9%, landings by weight have increased by 7%, and their value by 17%.
- **Demersal active gear**, on the other hand, make up 32% of the fishing days, consuming 68% of the energy and landing 33% of the fish by weight. Since 2018, demersal active gear have seen a 15% drop in energy use, along with a 32% decrease in landings by weight and a 5% drop in value.

Table 2-2 Fleet activity in the Northeast Atlantic region in 2022 and recent trends

Scale	Fishery	Fishing days		Energy consumption		landings in weight		Landings in value					
		(thousand days)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(million litres)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(thousand tonnes)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(million EUR)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total
SSF	Passive	415,6	-9%	30%	32,6	-16%	4%	85,9	4%	5%	377,9	12%	11%
	Active/mixed	290,1	4%	21%	14,3	-22%	2%	70,7	11%	4%	153,0	25%	5%
	Pelagic active	7,6	-9%	1%	0,9	-50%	0%	8,3	2%	0%	9,4	8%	0%
	Demersal active	166,0	-35%	12%	19,7	-19%	3%	38,8	-20%	2%	123,2	-11%	4%
LSF	Passive	157,4	-10%	11%	81,8	-6%	11%	142,6	9%	8%	534,8	21%	16%
	Active/mixed	8,5	-31%	1%	5,1	-36%	1%	10,4	-22%	1%	27,7	-31%	1%
	Pelagic active	51,7	-20%	4%	112,4	-20%	15%	895,4	-18%	49%	595,1	-7%	18%
	Demersal active	280,0	-10%	20%	504,9	-15%	65%	565,1	-32%	31%	1.505,5	-5%	45%
North-East Atlantic total		1.377,0	-12%	100%	771,8	-15%	100%	1.817,0	-20%	100%	3.326,6	1%	100%

Data source: MS data submissions under the 2024 Fleet Economic data call (EC-JRC-STEFCF, 2024); All monetary values adjusted for inflation; constant prices (2022).

Figure notes: (1) Results are estimates of the fishing activity by region based on the data and regional analysis methodology developed and used in STECF AER reports; (2) regional totals may not add up to EU totals due to incomplete data submissions (e.g., missing spatial information for one or more variables; see 2024 AER Methodology for more details).

Mediterranean Sea EU fisheries

The EU fleet operating in the Mediterranean region leads in fishing days, with 64% of the total fishing days. However, it uses just 24% of the energy. The region contributes to only 10% of landings by weight but 23% of the total value. Since 2018, activity in the region has seen a 36% drop in energy use and a 25% decrease in landings by weight (Table 2-3).

- **SSF** dominates the Mediterranean, accounting for 81% of fishing days, while contributing 19% in energy use and 16% to landings by weight and 28% in value. SSF has experienced reductions in energy consumption (-20%), and landings by weight and value (both down by 22%) since 2018.
- **LSF** in the regions contributes to 84% of landings by weight and 72% by value. Since 2018, LSF in the Mediterranean has reduced energy consumption by 39% while seeing a 26% decrease in landings by weight and 25% in value.
- **Passive gear** is the main component of the Mediterranean fleet, accounting for 78% of the fishing days, but consuming only 20% of the energy. Although passive gear contributes less to landings by weight (17%), it accounts for 30% of the landed value. Energy use by passive gear has fallen by 22% since 2018, while landings by weight have dropped by 23%.
- **Demersal active gear** is responsible for 68% of energy use, contributing 31% to landings by weight and 43% to landed value. Since 2018, demersal active gear has seen a 39% reduction in energy use and a 33% drop in landings by weight.

Table 2-3 Fleet activity in the Mediterranean Sea region in 2022 and recent trends

Scale	Fishery	Fishing days			Energy consumption			landings in weight			Landings in value		
		(thousand days)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(million litres)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(thousand tonnes)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total	(million EUR)	%Δ 2022-2018	As % of total
SSF	Passive	2446,6	-20%	76%	62,0	-19%	16%	44,5	-24%	13%	370,8	-25%	24%
	Active/mixed	126,8	8%	4%	4,6	-34%	1%	5,1	11%	2%	39,9	18%	3%
	Pelagic active	16,1	-10%	0%	1,0	-20%	0%	2,2	-27%	1%	6,4	-25%	0%
	Demersal active	33,7	-43%	1%	4,2	-20%	1%	2,6	-28%	1%	12,8	-25%	1%
LSF	Passive	76,6	-37%	2%	14,8	-35%	4%	10,6	-19%	3%	83,9	-8%	5%
	Active/mixed	1,4	-19%	0%	0,2	-53%	0%	0,4	2%	0%	1,2	-31%	0%
	Pelagic active	100,5	-18%	3%	41,6	-34%	11%	167,1	-21%	50%	375,6	-9%	25%
	Demersal active	429,4	-24%	13%	255,6	-39%	67%	98,5	-33%	30%	638,3	-33%	42%
Mediterranean Sea total		3231,0	-21%	100%	384,1	-36%	100%	331,0	-25%	100%	1528,9	-24%	100%

Data source: MS data submissions under the 2024 Fleet Economic data call (EC-JRC-STEFCF, 2024); All monetary values adjusted for inflation; constant prices (2022).

Figure notes: (1) Results are estimates of the fishing activity by region based on the data and regional analysis methodology developed and used in STECF AER reports; (2) regional totals may not add up to EU totals due to incomplete data submissions (e.g., missing spatial information for one or more variables; see 2024 AER Methodology for more details).

2.1.2 Aquaculture in Europe

Marine aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic, Mediterranean and Black Sea regions plays a significant role in the region's social and economic landscape. The sector contributes to food security, job creation, and economic development, especially in coastal and remote areas, and production has been increasing over time (Figure 2-1).

Figure 2-1 Marine aquaculture production (in tonnes) in the Northeast Atlantic (FAO area 27) and the Mediterranean and Black Sea (FAO area 37).

Data source: FAO. 2024. FishStat: Global aquaculture production 1950-2022. [Accessed on 29 March 2024]. In: FishStatJ. Available at www.fao.org/fishery/en/statistics/software/fishstatj. Licence: CC-BY-4.0.) from 1950-2022.

Table 2-4 and Table 2-5 present production statistics (in volume and value) by country for marine aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean & Black Sea regions, based on FAO, 2024.

Overall, aquaculture production across Europe’s seas varies regionally in terms of production volume and value, with a notable focus on shellfish production and a mix of small and large-scale operations. The contributions differ by region:

- Northern Europe: Norway, Iceland, and Finland primarily focus on high-value finfish such as salmon and trout.
- Southern Europe: Mediterranean countries (e.g., Greece, Italy, and Spain) focus on diverse species, including seabass, seabream, and shellfish.
- Atlantic Coast: Countries like Ireland and the UK contribute significantly to both finfish and shellfish aquaculture.

Aquaculture production in the Northeast Atlantic region

In the Northeast Atlantic region, EU countries accounted for 18% of the total marine aquaculture production volume and 9% of the total value in 2022. EU production represented only 2% of finfish production but accounted for over 95% of the total shellfish production in both volume and value.

Norway was the top producer in the region, contributing 65% of the total volume and 73% of the value in 2022. Among EU countries, Spain and France were the leading producers, contributing to 7% and 6% of the total production, respectively.

Table 2-4 Aquaculture activity in the Northeast Atlantic region in 2022

Country	Finfish		Molluscs		Crustaceans		Algae		Total production	
	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$
Denmark	9790	48838	8556	5431			0		18346	54270
Estonia	295	1577							295	1577
Finland	12980	77902							12980	77902
France		878	147729	590738			182	625	147911	592241
Germany			8681	13653					8681	13653
Ireland	11916	106949	31207	79469			493		43616	186418
Netherlands	20	211	33090	57437					33110	57648
Portugal	3905	22789	9302	96723					13207	119511
Spain	3476	32988	187647	162187					191123	195175
Sweden			2346	2783					2346	2783
Channel Islands		0	1190	3504					1190	3504
Faroe Islands	108630	614063	85	324			30	117	108745	614504
Iceland	44936	365394	12	114					44948	365508
Norway	1644732	11070903	2646	2014	1	1	60	129	1647439	11073047
Russian Federation	83245	610739	90	132				16	83335	610888
United Kingdom	174338	1131291	19107	41202					193445	1172494
Region total	2098263	14084522	451688	1055711	1	1	765	887	2550717	15141123
EU total	42382	292132	428558	1008421	0	0	675	625	471615	1301178
%share EU	2%	2%	95%	96%	0%	0%	88%	70%	18%	9%

Data source: FAO. 2024 FishStat: Global aquaculture production 1950-2022. [Accessed on 29 March 2024]. In: FishStatJ. Available at www.fao.org/fishery/en/statistics/software/fishstatj. Licence: CC-BY-4.0. from 1950-2022.

Aquaculture production in the Mediterranean & Black Sea regions

In the Mediterranean and Black Sea region in 2022, EU countries contributed to 39% of the total marine aquaculture production volume and 44% of the total value. EU production covered 30% of finfish production and 93% of total shellfish production. In terms of value, this corresponded to 41% of finfish production and 89% of shellfish production.

Türkiye was the top producer in the region, responsible for 41% of the total volume and 38% of the value in 2022. Greece and Italy were the top EU producers, contributing 15% and 11% of the total production volume, respectively.

In the Mediterranean Sea region, finfish represents over 86% of the volume and 92% of the value of the whole aquaculture production. Finfish (spt. seabass and seabream) are mainly produced in sea cages located in both coastal and offshore areas of most of the countries, especially in Turkey, Greece, Spain and Croatia. In recent years, up to 15 499 cages have been counted in the Mediterranean area (Papageorgiou et al., 2021). Minor production is also performed in land-based tanks and brackish basins.

Table 2-5 Aquaculture activity in the Mediterranean Sea region in 2022

Country	Finfish		Molluscs		Crustaceans		Algae		Total production	
	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$	tonnes	thousand \$
Bulgaria			1420	1588					1420	1588
Croatia	21852	172766	1113	2718					22964	175484
Cyprus	7513	49461			12	169			7524	49631
France	5039	47687	10129	43114	2	44			15170	90844
Greece	128696	881894	10749	6418	155	532			139601	888845
Italy	13921	114296	85354	285390	24	349			99299	400034
Malta	18051	337428							18051	337428
Slovenia	86	693	536	626					622	1319
Spain	40636	406488	6257	11008					46893	417496
Albania	6574	35593	922	816					7496	36408
Algeria	2885	18328	55	211	0	0			2940	18539
Bosnia and Herzegovina	110	681	40	80					150	761
Egypt	145148	709457			1665	27659			146813	737116
Israel	3427	28496							3427	28496
Lebanon	3	13			10	120			13	133
Montenegro	141	880	225	885					366	1765
Morocco	190	1495	318	5586			174	17	682	7098
Tunisia	19807	104297	37	168			79	18	19923	104483
Türkiye	363227	2052824	5494	9287					368721	2062111
Region total	777306	4962775	122648	367894	1868	28872	253	35	902075	5359577
EU total	235794	2010713	115558	350862	193	1094	0	0	351544	2362669
%share EU	30%	41%	94%	95%	10%	4%	0%	0%	39%	44%

Data source: FAO. 2024 FishStat: Global aquaculture production 1950-2022. [Accessed on 29 March 2024]. In: FishStatJ. Available at www.fao.org/fishery/en/statistics/software/fishstatj. Licence: CC-BY-4.0. from 1950-2022.

Bivalve mollusc farming covers about 14% of the volume and 7% of the value of Mediterranean aquaculture. The production is mainly represented by mussels farmed in long-line systems in coastal areas of Spain, Italy, Greece and France. The Manila clam is mainly farmed on the bottom in brackish waters, especially in Italy, which is the top EU producer, although the production has been recently severely affected by the invasion of the non-native blue crab *Callinectes sapidus*. Oyster is a minor farmed species in the region, although production is increasing. Its cultivation is carried out both in brackish basins and in coastal areas mainly in suspended systems (e.g., rafts, lanterns, bags, on-rope), and off-bottom in floating systems (bags, long-line baskets).

Crustaceans still represent a minor aquaculture sector, and algae aquaculture farming has not yet been developed, especially in European countries.

2.2 Towards assessing pressures and impacts of fisheries and aquaculture on the marine biodiversity and ecosystem at regional level

The following analysis represents the first comprehensive effort to assess the impact of fisheries and aquaculture activities in Europe's seas. It is based on the ICES ecosystem overview framework (ICES 2023b), with the added value of an in-depth focus on both sectors, which is unprecedented in its level of detail. Fisheries and aquaculture are categorised by different production systems to evaluate their impacts on key ecosystem components. As an iterative process, the analysis will be refined over time, integrating an expanding knowledge base, improving the spatial resolution, and other advancements.

2.2.1 The approach

The ICES Ecosystem Overviews are comprehensive reports that provide a detailed analysis of the main human pressures on marine ecosystems and their impacts. These overviews are designed to support ecosystem-based management (EBM) by offering science-based insights into the state of various marine ecosystems. Key features of the ICES Ecosystem Overviews are:

- Risk-Based Methods: They use risk-based methods to identify and explain how human activities affect key ecosystem components in each ICES ecoregion.
- Trends and Context: The overviews provide information on recent trends in the ecosystem, offering a crucial context for managing human activities sustainably.
- Human Pressures: They highlight the main human pressures, such as fishing, pollution, habitat degradation and climate change, and their effects on marine ecosystems.
- Integrated Advice: The overviews are part of ICES' approach to delivering integrated, ecosystem-informed advice, considering multiple human pressures and environmental processes.

ICES Ecosystem Overviews cover various ecoregions in the Northeast Atlantic, including the Azores, Baltic Sea, Barents Sea, Bay of Biscay and the Iberian coast, Celtic Seas, Central Arctic Ocean, Faroes, Greater North Sea, Greenland Sea, Icelandic Waters, Norwegian Sea and Oceanic Northeast Atlantic.

For this study, we used the ICES ecosystem overviews framework to zoom into fisheries and aquaculture activities and provide a detailed analysis of the direct interactions between the different subsectors for fisheries and aquaculture and the pressures exerted over the various ecosystem components. We adapted the methodology developed by ICES to produce Sankey diagrams (ICES, 2023b).

The first step of the analysis was to subdivide the fisheries and aquaculture activities into sectors.

Secondly, we produced two matrices (in XLS format) indicating the pressures created by each sector and which pressures affect which ecosystem state components (annexes 1-3 and 5 in ICES 2023b). Only the direct links between sector and pressure and ecosystem components were considered.

The pressures considered were: physical abrasion, introduction of contaminating compounds, invasive species, marine litter, noise, sediment siltation/smothering and marine living resources extraction.

The ecosystem components considered were: benthic habitats (& associated biota): non-VMEs, benthic habitats (& associated biota), VMEs, cephalopods, elasmobranchs, fish, food web (MSFD D4), marine mammals, pelagic habitats (& associated biota), reptiles and seabirds. These are the stage 1 linkage frameworks (tables A1.1-A1.4 in Annex 1).

Thirdly, we developed a risk assessment using categorical scores for i) spatial extent overlap, ii) frequency of occurrence and iii) degree of impact for each of the direct linkages identified in the previous step (stage 2 linkage frameworks, tables A1.5-A1.8 in Annex 1).

The templates for this work are available at ICES 2023b. The adapted matrices for fisheries and aquaculture are provided in Annex 1.

This exercise was carried out by the task members with expertise in fisheries and aquaculture in the ICES area (Northeast Atlantic) and the Mediterranean Sea.

These products represent a first attempt to describe the impact of fisheries and aquaculture in the marine environment in detail (i.e., by sector). They are divided by sector (fisheries and aquaculture) and by region (Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea).

All the assumptions, limitations, caveats and potential of this analysis are detailed in section 2.2.4.

Data product - Fisheries

For commercial fisheries, we decomposed the activity into small and large vessels, active and passive gear, demersal and pelagic fisheries, and combinations therein. Reduction fisheries (with vessels above 40 metres in length that target foraging fish species for fishmeal production) are also identified as a large contributor to the removal of marine living resources, which catch large volumes of fish not destined for human consumption. Such combinations were considered tractable, with a minimal number of categories required to capture the main contrasting effects between types of fisheries.

The selected/relevant combinations between categories were:

1. Passive pelagic gear (i.e., gillnets, driftnets, traps, handlines, drifting longlines, etc.).
2. Passive demersal gear (i.e., pots, traps, set longlines, set gillnets, etc.).
3. Small vessels (< 12 m) using pelagic trawls.
4. Small vessels (< 12 m) using mobile bottom-contacting gear (bottom trawls, dredges, etc.).
5. Large vessels (> 12 m) using pelagic trawls.
6. Large vessels (> 12 m) using mobile bottom-contacting gear (bottom trawls, dredges, etc.).
7. Large vessels (> 40 m) involved in reduction fisheries i.e., targeting foraging fish species.

Data product - Aquaculture

For aquaculture, the activities were subdivided into the following sectors:

- High trophic production systems.
- Low trophic production systems.
- Algae sea-based.
- Coastal versus offshore.
- Polyculture systems, both sea-based and coastal, were identified as farming methods in our analysis, but were excluded from the final analysis due to the limited production as well as the literature and data available at present.

The final categories analysed were:

Species (e.g., finfish, shrimps) whose farming is entirely dependent on the use of external feeds or fertilisers:

1. High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens).
2. High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens).
3. High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks).
4. High trophic species: land-based recirculating aquaculture system (RAS tanks).

Species (e.g., bivalve shellfish) whose farming is entirely dependent on natural processes or nutrients coming from other anthropogenic activity than the aquaculture farm; or fish species (e.g., mullets) whose farming is dependent on some supplementary feed or fertilisers in addition to the natural process:

5. Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft.
6. Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom.
7. Low trophic species: land-based RAS tanks.

Species of seaweeds whose farming is dependent entirely on natural processes:

8. Algae sea-based.

The spreadsheets with direct linkages from activity-pressure-ecosystem components are available in Annex 1.

2.2.2 Technical specifications of the analysis

Technically, the analysis can be broken into two stages. Due to the large number of human pressure and environmental pressure combinations with ecosystem components that have to be scored, the first stage in the analysis is to identify direct links between human activities and pressures, and then, assuming independence, identify direct links between pressure and ecosystem components. This was done by filling out 2 separated matrices in an XLS document. This first stage allows the production of a reduced set of sector - pressure - ecosystem component combinations.

The second stage is to provide scores for the reduced set of sector-pressure-ecosystem component direct linkages. In the second stage, experts used categorical scores for spatial extent overlap (“Extent”),

frequency of occurrence (“Frequency”) and degree of impact (“DoI”) for each of the direct linkages identified in the first stage to develop a risk assessment of the possible impact(s) of different fisheries and aquaculture activities on the various ecosystem components, considering direct impacts only (ICES, 2021).

Scoring the “Extent” requires a broad-scale knowledge of the activities taking place in an ecoregion. Categories were defined as follows (see ICES 2023b):

- **Exogenous** (E, activity occurs outside of the area occupied by the ecosystem component, the pressures would reach the ecosystem component through dispersal).
- **Site** (S, > 0-5% overlap).
- **Local** (L, 5-50%).
- **Widespread patchy** (WP, > 50%).
- **Widespread even** (WE, > 50%).

Scoring the “Frequency” (in an average year), categories were defined as follows:

- **Rare** (R, e.g. occurs in one month per year).
- **Occasional** (O, e.g. occurs in 4 months per year).
- **Common** (C, e.g. occurs in 8 months per year).
- **Persistent** (P, e.g. occurs in every month of the year).

Scoring “DoI” consisted of assigning 1 (low) to 3 (high) as interpreted using the Options for Delivering Ecosystem-Based Marine Management (ODEMM) guidelines:

- **Low** (L) is assigned to a pressure not considered to (currently) produce population level/functional group effects.
- **Chronic** (C) is assigned to pressures that may have a population level/functional effect if they have a high enough spatial and or temporal occurrence (i.e., chronic nature).
- **Acute** (A) is assigned where acute (immediate) impacts are expected/known to occur.

Such scoring was in diversion from the [ODEMM](#) methodology, but still in line with ICES methodology.

During the analysis, each categorical score is assigned a value between 0 and 1 (Table 2-6).

Table 2-6 Scoring categories and corresponding categorical scores and values used in the analysis.

Categories	Categorical Scores	Value
Overlap	WE	1
	WP	0.67
	L	0.33
	S	0.03
	E	0.01
Frequency	P	1
	C	0.67
	O	0.33
	R	0.08
DoI	A	1
	C	0.2
	L	0.05

Impact risk scores per linkage chain were calculated as the product of the assigned three categorical scores (i.e., spatial extent value x frequency of occurrence value x degree of impact value).

Code

All code developed for this analysis was written in the ICES Transparent Assessment Framework structure ([Transparent Assessment Framework](#)). Two repositories were created, one for the conversion of the matrices created in stage 1 into the format required for the risk analysis in stage 2. And one for the creation of the Sankey diagrams from the filled-out risk analyses.

The code developed is publicly available (ICES 2024a, b). This code reads from XLS files and produces a CSV file containing one row for each linkage, complete with columns containing formulas to convert the codes above into their numerical values. These files were pasted into a Google Sheets file and were filled in by the experts.

The code for the second stage and the production of the Sankey diagrams was based on code developed for an ODEMM analysis of the Celtic Seas (https://github.com/PaulBouch/ODEMM_Celtic_Sea). It reads directly from the Google Sheets and produces all the Sankey diagrams.

Sankey diagram production

Sankey diagrams are composed of three vertical pillars that represent the activity in sectors (left), the pressures generated (middle), and the ecosystem component directly affected (right). The flow connects the sectors with pressures with the ecosystem components. The height of the flow is proportional to the total risk identified for that connection, making it easy to visualise the largest contributions by sector.

Risks for each connection are computed by summing up the risks across its components. The height of the graph can be thought of as representing the total risk after filtering out elements that have a small impact, and all remaining connections are proportional to this. For example (the following percentages are approximate and for illustration purposes only), for fisheries in the Northeast Atlantic, ‘Large vessels - active demersal’ comprise 25% of the total risk, and ‘Small vessels - active demersal’ 22%, and so on. Within ‘Large vessels - active demersal’, ‘Living Resources Extraction’ comprises 46% of the risk for that sector and 12% of the total risk for the region. Similarly, for pressure, the height of ‘Living Resources Extraction’

corresponds to 77% of the total risk, and 56% of this leads to pressure on the 'Fish' ecological characteristic, which corresponds to 43% of the total risk. Finally, in terms of ecological characteristics, 'Fish' receive 47% of the total risk, with 93% of this coming from 'Living Resources Extraction'. Essentially, the code computes these summaries and uses a prewritten method to produce the Sankey diagrams.

2.2.3 Results

The results of the regional analysis are presented using Sankey diagrams (see Figure 2-2-Figure 2-5)

The Sankey diagrams for fisheries aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean regions visually represent the relationships among fisheries activities and among aquaculture activities, in isolation, the pressures they exert, and the ecosystem components affected in the respective ecoregions. The diagrams are visually complicated, and the analyses address diverse types of fishing and aquaculture practices throughout these large regions (FAO Fishing Areas 27 and 37). That said, the analysis has some key take-aways described below.

The different sectors or types of fisheries and aquaculture are represented on the left side of the diagrams. Each flow, colour-coded based on the activity and pressure, highlights how specific sectors impact ecosystem components. The width of the flow linking sectors to pressures and ecosystem components signifies the intensity of the contribution. For example, the flow from "high trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)" to "living resources extraction" and onward to "fish" is relatively thick, indicating a major impact for this type of aquaculture.

The Sankey diagrams effectively illustrate the complex interactions between sectors, pressures, and the resulting ecosystem impacts, providing a clear overview of the dominant pressures and the ecosystem components most affected in these ecoregions by fisheries and aquaculture.

Northeast Atlantic fisheries

The Sankey diagram for the Northeast Atlantic fisheries identifies living resources extraction as the major pressure exerted by all fisheries sectors. The main impact is on fish, even though other ecosystem components like food webs and elasmobranchs are considerably affected.

Other pressures exerted by fisheries ranked by relative contribution are abrasion, noise, siltation/smothering and marine litter. The main contributors to abrasion and noise are large vessels using mobile bottom contacting gear (large active vessels demersal) followed by small vessels fishing with mobile bottom contacting gear.

Figure 2-2 Sankey diagram for fisheries in the Northeast Atlantic.

Note: From left to right, the columns show the activity divided into sectors, the pressures in the middle and the ecosystem components affected on the right-hand side. The flows coming out from each activity to the pressure and then to the ecosystem components are colour-coded. The width of the flow determines the relative contribution of the sector-pressure-impact linkage. The height of the columns for sector, pressure and ecosystem shows their relative contribution.

Mediterranean Sea fisheries

Likewise, the Sankey diagram for the Mediterranean Sea fisheries identifies marine living resources extraction as the main pressure exerted by all fisheries sectors. As opposed to the Northeast Atlantic assessment, the impacts are more evenly distributed across fish, cephalopods and other ecosystem components, possibly reflecting the multispecies nature of fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea.

Physical abrasion remains as the second pressure affecting a number of ecosystem components, being driven in particular by large vessels using mobile bottom contacting gear types (large vessels-active demersal), followed by small vessels, the latter generating a minor contribution to the abrasion.

Marine litter ranks as the third pressure in the Mediterranean Sea, and passive pelagic vessels are the fishery sector that mostly contributes to generating this pressure. Finally, sediment siltation ranks the lowest in the pressure assessment. Both pressures are mostly generated by large vessels-active demersal, showing that the latter sector generates the larger variety of pressures (and the most relevant contribution to the overall impact risk score). Notably, the most vulnerable species groups (marine mammals, reptiles and seabirds) are affected mainly by pelagic fisheries using passive gear.

Figure 2-3 Sankey diagram for fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea.

Note: From left to right, the columns show the activity divided into sectors, the pressures in the middle, and the ecosystem component that is affected on the right-hand side. The flows coming out from each activity to the pressure and then to the ecosystem components are colour-coded. The width of the flow determines the relative contribution of the sector-pressure-impact linkage. The height of the columns for sector, pressure and ecosystem shows their relative contribution.

Aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic region

The Sankey diagram for aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic region (FAO Fishing Area 27) identifies marine living resources extraction as the most prominent pressure exerted by almost all aquaculture sectors in the region. Other significant pressures include interactions with wild organisms (e.g., escaped farmed salmon and wild salmon behavioural interactions, genetic introgression, and disease/parasite spread), marine litter, invasive species, and noise, along with others like siltation, nutrient enrichment, and substrate loss. Low-trophic sea-based culture systems and algae culture showed the lowest pressure on ecosystem components by comparison.

The height of the lines representing each pressure indicates its relative contribution to the ecosystem's impact. Fish, pelagic habitats, and food webs (MSFD D4) are the primary ecosystem components impacted by aquaculture activities, particularly due to living resource production. Unlike the Mediterranean region, some fisheries in the Northeast Atlantic do supply the fish feed industry (e.g., fish meal and fish oil). Other affected components include marine mammals, seabirds, cephalopods, and benthic habitats, with varying degrees of impact from different pressures.

Figure 2-4 Sankey diagram for aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic.

Note: From left to right, the columns show the industry divided into sectors, the pressures in the middle, and the ecosystem component affected on the right-hand side. The flows coming out from each activity to the pressure and then to the ecosystem components are colour coded. The width of the flow determines the relative contribution of the sector-pressure-impact linkage. The height of the columns for sector, pressure and ecosystem shows the relative contribution.

Aquaculture in the Mediterranean Sea region

The Sankey diagram for Mediterranean aquaculture identifies the farming of high trophic species in coastal areas as the most impacting culture system, mainly due to the pressure exerted by farming activities on benthic habitat and associated biota and due to the ecological interactions with wild populations, mainly fish. When net pen culture systems are moved offshore, both pressures have a lower degree of impact. The introduction of invasive species and associated organisms is the most relevant pressure exerted by the culture of low trophic species, both online (e.g., mussels) and on the seabed (e.g., Manila clam) and by algae farming. Living resources extraction is recorded among the most important pressures in the Northeast Atlantic, whilst it is not relevant in the Mediterranean area, being the ingredients for feed manufacturing (e.g., fish meal and fish oil) imported and not fished for in the Mediterranean region.

Other pressures, in order of importance by relative contributions, are: nutrient enrichment, noise, siltation, marine litter (mainly from farming of low trophic species), substrate loss, living resource extraction and abrasion.

Figure 2-5 Sankey diagram for aquaculture in the Mediterranean region.

Note: From left to right, the columns show the activity divided into sectors, the pressures in the middle, and the ecosystem component that is affected on the right-hand side. The flows coming out from each activity to the pressure and then to the ecosystem components are colour-coded. The width of the flow determines the relative contribution of the sector-pressure-impact linkage. The height of the columns for sector, pressure and ecosystem shows their relative contribution.

2.2.4 Limitations and Next Steps

This analysis marks the first attempt to comprehensively assess the impact of various fisheries and aquaculture sectors on the marine environment in EU waters. For fisheries, we have categorised activities into seven distinct groups, while for aquaculture, we have identified eight categories. This approach is novel in its detailed scale for fisheries and aquaculture. As an iterative process, the assessment will be refined over time, benefiting from an expanding knowledge base and enhanced spatial resolution, among other improvements.

Limitations/caveats of the current product:

- A spatial resolution: the regional analysis is currently based on the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean regions.
- A semi-quantitative approach for scoring to strengthen: the approach included joint scoring meetings to enable consistent interpretation of impact scores. However, a post hoc assessment would be needed to consolidate scores, especially for those pressures whose impact is less known (e.g., benthic impact, litter, noise) and enhance comparability among regions/sectors.
- The result of the assessment is a unitless index, and it does not provide any information on pressures and impacts on an absolute scale. Instead, it gives information on the relative magnitude between different areas within the assessment period. The results of such cumulative impact assessment are best considered as a means of communicating the patterns and intensities of pressures and impacts within different regions and sectors (i.e., fisheries and aquaculture) and highlighting the ecosystem components that are relatively under the most severe cumulative pressures and impacts.
- Reference period/baseline: the assessment may not hold long into the future when/if the implementation of management measures developed to mitigate the pressures, and also given ongoing long-lasting environmental changes. In this respect, additional pressure layers could be added to anticipate such future changes. For example, O’Hara et al. (2023) found that one important addition is the inclusion of mean sea surface temperature (SST) as a stressor based on species’ thermal tolerances, in addition to the SST extremes stressor (i.e., marine heat waves) included in the cumulative impact assessment.
- Integration of fisheries and aquaculture datasets into a single evaluation frame is not possible due to the different (spatial) scale between the two activities.
- Consensus about the inclusion of microplastic in marine litter. Microplastics are widespread in the seas and are classified into two types: primary and secondary microplastics. Primary microplastics are intentionally manufactured small plastic particles that are released directly into the environment. Secondary microplastics result from the breakdown of larger plastic items through processes like weathering, UV radiation, and physical abrasion. Hence, because microplastics are not a direct effect of the activities compared to the macroplastics that fisheries and aquaculture activities can generate, they were left aside from the present evaluation despite the relevant impacts of microplastics on the marine environment.
- Ghost fishing — caused by abandoned, lost, or discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) — poses a substantial threat to marine ecosystems. While this analysis does not formally classify ALDFG as a direct pressure on the marine environment, it was carefully considered when assessing the link between sectors, pressures, and ecosystem components, leading to its inclusion in marine (macro)litter scoring.

- Cumulative impacts are not accounted for, as Degrees of Impact (DoI) were scored independently per pressure. The approach developed so far has not included possible non-linear responses between pressures and states and synergistic and antagonistic effects in the model. There are many examples of non-linear relationships, such as ecosystem thresholds when stressors exceed some value (e.g., Kraberg et al., 2011; Clark et al., 2016). However, little is currently known about where, when or why non-additive responses occur (Crain et al., 2008; Darling and Côté, 2008), and thus the [additive model](#) remains the default option of such approaches. Besides this, some pressures accumulate and persist in the environment over time. Hence, many pollutants, such as metals, plastic litter, or chemicals, persist in the environment, causing effects that can, for example, amplify climate change.
- Information on the uncertainty/confidence alongside the scoring is not provided at this stage.

Further developments:

- A more advanced (i.e., objective) method to describe the spatial dimension and overlap between pressures more explicitly would be needed. However, ensuring coherence among data spatial layers is also key when combining layers. In (pressure x ecosystem components) matrices, such an approach would also typically use qualitative impact scores to account for the magnitude of the effect of each pressure on each component (e.g., Korpinen et al. 2021).
- Degree of impact scoring revision: the scoring, in particular scores associated with certain pressures generated by fishing and aquaculture (e.g., impact on benthic habitat, marine litter, ghost nets, noise), could benefit from a further revision/update, taking into account progress achieved in, e.g., the latest MSFD assessments and Common Implementation Strategy Task groups).
- Resolution: a further subdivision should take place to detect subregional differences that are compatible with the subdivision of marine regions of other EU directives (i.e., MSFD). The expansion of the assessments towards other regions (e.g., the Baltic and Black Seas) could also be explored.
- Scoring for uncertainty/confidence should be incorporated in further iterations.

3 Actionable solutions and mitigation measures to support sustainable fisheries and aquaculture

Key messages

Fisheries management through science-based catch limits and monitoring: Establishing catch limits and quotas based on scientific assessments, combined with effective monitoring and enforcement, is essential for sustainable fisheries management. This approach has been effective in increasing fish populations, as demonstrated in the Northeast Atlantic, and helps counter overfishing trends, especially when supplemented by area-based management to protect essential and vulnerable habitats and the use of selective fishing gear to minimise bycatch and habitat impact.

Combating Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated (IUU) fishing: Strengthening monitoring, surveillance, and enforcement efforts across the EU, along with leveraging advanced monitoring technologies, helps to detect and prevent IUU fishing. This approach supports the sustainability of marine resources, protecting legal fisheries, and enhances cooperation among EU Member States to uphold marine protection regulations.

Adoption of Sustainable Aquaculture Practices: Emphasizing the use of environmentally friendly technologies and methods to reduce the impact on ecosystems and biodiversity, nutrient discharges, marine litter, chemical and pharmaceutical releases, and interactions with wild species. Reducing the ecological footprint of fish feed and improving biosecurity and animal welfare practices.

Enhancing Aquaculture Resilience and Efficiency: Improving resilience to climate change with effective long-lasting and adaptive strategies. Streamlining regulatory processes to foster sustainable growth and to enhance ecosystem services of aquaculture.

3.1 Common transition objectives

In the Northeast Atlantic, Mediterranean, and Black Sea regions, several international bodies, including the European Commission (EC), European Environment Agency (EEA), Regional Seas Conventions (OSPAR, HELCOM, Barcelona Convention, Black Sea Convention), RFMOs (e.g., GFCM), marine science institutions (e.g., ICES), stakeholders' advisory councils (e.g., MEDAC), Environment program of the United Nations (UNEP), and others, work collaboratively to set transition objectives, targets and monitoring programmes to support sustainable marine fisheries and aquaculture.

Transition objectives define the goals and actions needed to promote sustainable practices and protect marine ecosystems. For maximum effectiveness, these objectives should be comprehensive, actionable, and aligned with overarching sustainability goals and policy frameworks. Table 3-1 summarises the primary transition objectives for marine ecosystems within EU and international policies, and Table 3-2 provides an overview of relevant monitoring programs and their associated legal instruments and funding mechanisms.

Table 3-1 Common transition objectives from national and international policies in Europe’s marine regions in support of sustainable fisheries and aquaculture.

Environmental Sustainability	Economic Viability	Social Responsibility	Governance and Policy Frameworks	Scientific Research and Data Collection
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ecosystem-Based Management: Implementing management practices that consider the entire ecosystem, including the interdependence of species and their habitats. ● Biodiversity Conservation: Protecting and restoring marine biodiversity through measures such as establishing marine protected areas (MPAs) and preserving critical habitats. ● Support for Sustainable Aquaculture: Promoting environmentally friendly aquaculture practices that minimise impacts on wild fish populations and habitats. ● Pollution Reduction: Reducing marine pollution from land-based and sea-based sources, including plastic waste, chemicals, and nutrients. ● Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation: Developing strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change on marine environments and adapting fisheries and aquaculture practices to changing conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainable Harvesting: Ensuring that fishing practices do not exceed the reproductive capacity of fish populations, thereby maintaining fish stocks at sustainable levels. ● Market Incentives: Creating market incentives for sustainably sourced seafood, including certification schemes and eco-labelling. ● Innovation and Technology: Encouraging the adoption of innovative technologies that enhance the sustainability and efficiency of fisheries and aquaculture operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community Engagement: Involving local communities in decision-making processes and ensuring that their knowledge and needs are considered in management plans. ● Livelihood Support: Supporting the livelihoods of coastal and fishing communities through sustainable economic opportunities and capacity-building initiatives. ● Equitable Access: Ensuring fair access to marine resources and space for all stakeholders, including small-scale fishers and small aquaculture farmers (marginalised groups). ● Food Security: Enhancing food security by ensuring that marine resources are managed sustainably and equitably distributed, with limited food waste. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM): Promoting the integrated management of coastal areas to address the complex interactions between land and sea activities. ● Regional Cooperation: Strengthening regional cooperation and coordination among countries to address transboundary issues and share best practices. ● Regulatory Compliance: Ensuring compliance with national and international regulations, including those set by the European Union (e.g., the Common Fisheries Policy) and international agreements (e.g. the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals). ● Monitoring and Enforcement: Enhancing monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to ensure adherence to sustainable practices and prevent illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data-Driven Science-Based Management: Utilising scientific data and research to inform management decisions and policies, ensuring they are based on the best available evidence. ● Stock Assessments: Conducting regular assessments of fish stocks to monitor their health and adjust management measures as needed. ● Assess the environmental impact of fisheries and aquaculture: Conducting thorough EIAs for fisheries and aquaculture projects to evaluate their potential impacts and identify mitigation measures.

While the objectives outlined in Table 3-1 are common across Europe's seas, each region may have specific priorities based on its unique environmental, economic, and social context (Bastardie et al., 2021).

The following sections present several short-term actionable solutions and mitigation measures to address the critical issues of overexploitation, habitat degradation, pollution, and climate change in fisheries and aquaculture.

3.2 Support to Sustainable Fisheries

Implement catch limits and quotas

Establishing catch limits and quotas (as output-control measures) based on scientific assessments, in combination with effective monitoring and enforcement, can significantly contribute to the sustainable management of fisheries. For example, the enforcement of catch limits has led to a significant increase in fish populations, demonstrating the effectiveness of this measure (see STECF, 2024, "ad hoc monitoring of the CFP" in 2023 for the **Northeast Atlantic stocks**), e.g., compared to a regulation of the fishing effort, or the use of technical measures only (input-control measures) (Cardinale et al., 2017).

Fisheries under effort control are prone to develop their ability to fish per unit of time to improve their productivity (so-called "technological creeping effects"). Any new gear or vessel improvement should be accompanied by a regulation implementing a decrease in effective effort to maintain or reduce the previous level of impact. This should prevent such a trend toward overfishing, which is likely if more efficient techniques for catching species are not regulated with quotas, as in areas like the **Mediterranean** where catch limits are not yet implemented for most stocks (only a few for large and small pelagic species). However, keeping the same efficiency is counterproductive when more efficient fishing is the target, for example, to save fuel use and reduce costs. Alternatively, promoting lower-impact fishing techniques yielding the same catch amount is a way to reduce costs, fuel, and impact.

In the specific case of the Mediterranean, implementing catch limits is challenging given the numerous landing places and unselective fishing (i.e., several species are caught within the same trip or fishing operation as in mixed stock fisheries), making it challenging to match catch allowances to actual catches. Hence, catch limits should be accompanied by other regulations. There are also mixed stock fisheries in the Northeast Atlantic area, especially fisheries targeting demersal fish species, including species without defined quotas, which are under threat of being overfished.

Implement area-based fisheries management

Implementing temporary fishing bans during critical life stages such as spawning seasons or juvenile aggregations can help enhance fish stock development. Such management should come with strict monitoring and enforcement measures to ensure compliance with these closures. This can help prevent illegal fishing activities and allow fish populations to recover effectively.

For example, area-based management could translate into complementing the areas that are currently designated in the EU fisheries technical measures regulation (EC, 2019) to prevent fishing in certain periods and areas as soon as the resources are deemed vulnerable or transition to a vulnerable state.

Besides closure to prevent fishing on commercial fish stocks during certain times and areas, designating and effectively managing marine protected areas (MPAs) is also crucial for safeguarding critical habitats and biodiversity. No-take zones should be implemented considering factors such as habitat connectivity,

size, and location of the protected areas to maximise their effectiveness in conserving marine ecosystems. Additionally, engaging local communities and stakeholders in the management of these protected areas can lead to greater success in preserving biodiversity and promoting sustainable fishing practices while preventing equity issues whenever access to specific or all fishing techniques is restricted.

For example, management plans could manage certain practices as in previously designated areas such as Natura 2000 sites set up after the EU Habitats Directive (EC, 1992) across EU Waters and designated by Member States to preserve hotspots of biodiversity, related to seabirds, marine mammals, turtles or elasmobranchs, or benthic communities, and any other types of nationally designated areas lacking a proper management plan (EEA on MPAs network e.g., <https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/biodiversity/natura-2000/natura-2000-coverage-in-european-seas-4>).

Selective fishing gear

Promoting the use of selective fishing gear and implementing bycatch reduction devices would help minimising the capture of non-target species, especially vulnerable species and juvenile fish. Additionally, it will be beneficial to implement restrictions on harmful fishing gear types that cause significant bycatch or habitat damage to preserve marine ecosystems and protect vulnerable species. For instance, the selectivity of the gear can be enhanced by increasing mesh sizes to allow smaller fish to escape, using sorting or grid devices on the gear to remove unwanted catch in the water rather than on the vessel's deck, employing innovative gear with AI-powered sensors to detect unwanted fish schools or release unwanted catch by opening the trawl into the water and implementing electronic monitoring to document the unwanted catch. This would involve using established protocols to compare the impact of the innovation with a baseline (Bastardie et al., 2024).

Contrasting IUU fishing

By improving monitoring and enforcement, the European Union (EU) can replicate successes and prevent illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing, ensuring the sustainability of our marine resources. By leveraging advanced monitoring technologies and increasing cooperation among Member States, the EU has effectively detected and prevented illegal fishing operations. For example, the prosecution of individuals and companies engaged in IUU fishing sends a strong deterrent message to would-be offenders. Besides, only marine fishery products accompanied by catch certificates validated by the competent flag state can be imported into the EU. The EU regularly updates the IUU vessel list. It includes IUU vessels identified by regional fisheries management organisations (EC, 2008b).

3.3 Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems

Habitat degradation represents one of the major drivers of marine biodiversity loss worldwide (Jaureguiberry et al., 2022). It may lead - among others - to the reduction of ecosystem services supported by marine ecosystems, including food provisioning. Several factors contribute to habitat degradation, like:

- Coastal development and defence against erosion, sediment loss (from sealing or sediment extraction), habitat fragmentation, etc.
- Overfishing and unsustainable fishing practices (in particular, mobile bottom-contacting fishing gears).
- Unsustainable aquaculture practices.
- Pollution, including chemical pollutants, nutrient runoff from agriculture and industry, plastic debris, macro litter including ALDFG and ghost fishing and micro-litter.
- Climate change, increase in ocean temperatures, and acidification.

Mitigating marine habitat degradation requires a combination of strategies related to managing the impacts of the factors contributing to habitat degradation, like pollution control and measures to combat overfishing (see 3.1), including adopting passive and active measures (e.g., MPAs and active restoration measures), and build on technological developments (innovative fishing gear, production practices, etc.). Examples of mitigation measures are:

Spatial protection measures of habitats

Pertaining to the direct protection of marine habitats, this approach is primarily conducted at the EU level by consolidating the Natura 2000 network, which includes Special Areas of Conservation (SACs, designated under the EU Habitats Directive (1992), to protect natural habitats and species that are of European interest, and Special Protection Areas (SPAs, defined under the EU Birds Directive (1979)), to protect bird species, particularly those that are rare, vulnerable, or migratory, and their critical habitats).

The coastal habitats typically protected under the Habitats Directive include coastal lagoons, mudflats and sandflats not covered by seawater at low tide, large shallow inlets and bays, coastal dunes, and salt marshes. In the marine context, the marine habitats protected by the Habitats Directive are *Posidonia* beds, estuaries, reefs, submerged or partially submerged sea caves, sandbanks which are slightly covered by seawater all the time, mudflats and seagrass beds, and submarine structures made by leaking gases.

The EU Action Plan for sustainable fishing - among others - calls for the protection of the seafloor by a voluntary phasing out of mobile bottom contacting gear in Natura 2000 sites by 2030. At the moment, there are likely no viable fishing technologies or innovative solutions in bottom trawling to mitigate the effect of bottom trawling in protected areas deemed vulnerable to physical abrasion (STOA, 2024). In addition, other conservation measures aimed to limit further pressures on vulnerable seabed habitats or sensitive species may be established in each Natura 2000 site, and because vulnerabilities differ, conservation measures shall be defined on a case-by-case approach to meet the conservation goal in the given (local) site.

Notably, the adoption of measures to protect marine habitats (e.g., prevention of abrasion from mobile bottom contacting gear, restriction of other activities affecting/disturbing the seafloor or benthic habitats) may generate positive effects in terms of enhancing carbon sink storage. Indeed, the restoration of particular habitats (like seagrass meadows, salt marshes and mangroves, and oyster beds) enhances (or restores) the so-called “blue carbon” sequestration (the sequestration of carbon in coastal/marine

ecosystems). Other measures to prevent habitat degradation, such as limiting bottom trawling (whose action on the seafloor might release labile organic carbon), are suspected to bring significant benefits in enhancing ocean carbon sequestration. However, the debate on the magnitude of bottom trawling in damaging carbon storage is still not concluded (see, for example, Sala et al., 2021; Hiddink et al., 2023).

Habitat restoration

Habitat restoration is now seen as an overarching goal that embraces not only passive measures (such as the establishment of spatial protection measures) but also active actions. Indeed, the recently adopted Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) (EC, 2024b) uses the following definition (Article 3(3)): ‘restoration’ means the process of actively or passively assisting the recovery of an ecosystem in order to improve its structure and functions with the aim of conserving or enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem resilience [...].

The restoration targets of the NRR include habitats protected under the Habitats Directive, habitats of species protected by the Directive, and other habitats up to 1000 m in depth. The regulation combines an overarching restoration objective for the long-term recovery of nature in the EU’s land and sea areas with binding restoration targets for specific habitats and species. These measures should cover at least 20% of the EU’s land and sea areas by 2030 and, ultimately, all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. Measures adopted by Member States (MS) to reach NRR restoration targets will need to be communicated to the EC by August 2026 in the context of the national Nature Restoration Plan.

Whilst passive measures rely typically on the spatial restriction of certain activities to prevent pressures, active measures are usually linked to concrete actions aimed at facilitating the recovery of certain habitats.

Active habitat restoration actions include different techniques that are developed according to the features of the habitats to be restored. In general terms, these techniques enable the restoration of habitats like seagrasses, mangroves, and oyster reefs, which provide breeding grounds and nurseries for many marine species. This approach implies a direct intervention on the seabed, which can include i) providing new substrate suitable for the settlement of the species/habitats to be restored (e.g., clutching for oyster beds), ii) transplanting of specimens on areas where habitats were destroyed (e.g., seagrass meadows; coralligenous species); iii) restocking by releasing specimens (from wild broods or in some cases farmed) in areas suitable for the establishment of the species (e.g. oyster reefs); iv) releasing larvae in areas suitable for their settlement (e.g., algal forests). Several projects aimed to apply such techniques have been and are being applied (some examples are provided below). The current focus is, in many cases, the upscale of the approach, given the logistic and economic cost constraints of its implementation.

The deployment of artificial reefs to enhance habitat complexity and provide shelter for marine organisms is another approach that is possible to implement to improve ocean productivity or increase species diversity. The structural complexity of artificial reefs may mimic natural habitats (such as rocky reefs or coral reefs), and such effects may be associated with the restoration process. However, such techniques need to be correctly implemented, particularly with proper design, site selection, and the use of biocompatible materials that prevent impacts on habitats of conservation/ecological value. The efficacy of artificial reefs to support the enhancement of fisheries resources in some cases has been questioned, as they may act more as a factor attracting species of certain ecological features (e.g., offering protection from predation) rather than supporting a proper increase in productivity (Komyakova et al., 2021)

Other actions that can trigger broadscale habitat recovery and restoration include the implementation of measures to reduce agricultural runoff and industrial discharge into marine environments, such as buffer zones and improved waste treatment systems. Such approaches are mainly developed in the context of the current EU legislation (e.g., WFD and Nitrate Directive, etc.) to reach the environmental targets (e.g., good ecological status) as defined by the appropriate policy instruments.

Examples of marine habitat restoration projects in the EU are:

[BLUE4ALL](#): This project aims to achieve effective management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) through targeted actions in 25 sites and living labs. It focuses on enhancing the resilience and connectivity of MPAs.

[OCEAN CITIZEN](#): This initiative tests an advanced restoration program that integrates ecological and societal interconnections. It aims to develop eco-engineering approaches to fisheries and aquaculture while enhancing carbon sequestration of marine habitats.

[MERCES \(Marine Ecosystem Restoration in Changing European Seas\)](#): This project worked across 128 restoration sites in Europe, focusing on habitats like seagrass beds and algal forests.

[AFRIMED](#): This project focuses on the restoration of Mediterranean marine forests, particularly those formed by *Cystoseira* species, which are crucial for biodiversity.

[BLUE CONNECT](#): This project aims to protect and restore marine habitats and ecosystems by developing a systematic approach to marine conservation planning and management across 12 demonstration sites.

[NEXT GENERATION EU - MARINE ECOSYSTEM RESTORATION](#): This project focuses on marine restoration of native oyster beds, seagrass meadows (typically *Posidonia oceanica*), algal forests and coralligenous in various sites along the Italian coast. The project includes the mapping of vulnerable habitats in the coastal and deep-sea areas, as well as the collection of macrolitter from sensitive habitats.

Improve waste management, initiate clean-up campaigns, implement fishing for litter activities and promote waste reduction strategies to tackle marine litter and plastic pollution.

Marine litter, predominantly plastic pollution, poses a grave threat to marine ecosystems, wildlife, and human health and also jeopardises economies that rely on healthy oceans (Horton, 2023). To combat this urgent global crisis, a comprehensive approach involving improved waste management, clean-up campaigns, fishing for litter initiatives, and waste reduction strategies is imperative.

Effective waste management is at the core of reducing marine litter (Helm et al., 2023). Inadequate disposal systems, insufficient recycling infrastructure, and poor waste collection services often lead to waste ending up in rivers, oceans, and along coastlines.

In the EU, abandoned, lost or discarded fishing gear, often referred to as 'ghost nets' account for about one-third of the marine litter found in Europe's seas (EC, 2019b). Ongoing efforts to address and mitigate the impact of ghost gear on marine environments under the European Union's Single-Use Plastics Directive (EC, 2019b) include:

1. **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR):** Producers of plastic fishing gear are required to cover the costs of waste collection, transport, and treatment from port reception facilities. This aims to ensure that fishing gear is properly managed and recycled.
2. **Port Reception Facilities Directive:** This directive mandates that ports provide adequate facilities for the disposal of waste, including fishing gear, and that ships deliver their waste to these facilities before departure. This helps prevent the discharge of waste at sea.
3. **Financial Support for Recovery:** The European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund provides financial support.
4. **Innovative Tracking and Recovery Projects:** Innovative projects like NETTAG+ are developing new methods for tracking and recovering lost fishing gear using acoustic tags and robotic systems.
5. **Awareness and Education Programs:** Targeted education and gear stewardship programs are being implemented to raise awareness among fishermen about the importance of retrieving lost gear and the environmental impact of ghost gear (Richardson, K., et al, 2021)

Clean-up campaigns, whether organised locally or globally, have proven to be an effective short-term solution for reducing marine litter. These campaigns raise awareness while actively removing waste from the environment. Collecting and analysing data on the types and sources of litter found during clean-ups is not just a task but a crucial step in the fight against marine litter (Consoli et al., 2020).

The 'Fishing for Litter' initiative encourages fishers to collect litter they encounter while fishing and bring it back to port for proper disposal. This not only reduces marine litter but also actively involves the fishing community in safeguarding the marine environment (Mannaart and Bentley, 2020). Ports should offer free disposal facilities. In some EU Member States, programs have been established to fund the collection and management of fishing gear waste and passively fished waste, including "fishing for litter" schemes. These initiatives are encouraged and should complement the cost recovery systems set by Directive 2019/883. The systems, based on a 100% indirect fee for MARPOL Annex V waste (excluding cargo residues), should not discourage fishing port communities from participating in these waste delivery programs.

Reducing the amount of waste produced, especially single-use plastics, is a long-term solution to combat marine litter. Governments, industries, and consumers must work together to implement policies that limit the production and use of single-use plastic items, replacing them with sustainable alternatives (Fortibuoni et al., 2023).

3.4 Support to sustainable aquaculture production systems

The aquaculture sector in Europe is diverse, encompassing a range of operations from low-input algae farms to intensive cultures of high-trophic species (Regional assessments), each exerting different environmental pressures on the surrounding ecosystems. The categories of pressures vary depending on the species, farming system, site, type of water resource used, and the sensitivity of the receiving environment.

Intensive aquaculture of high trophic species inflicts pressures on aquatic ecosystems due to, inter alia, organic and nutrient discharges, the release of chemicals, the introduction of alien species, escapes of selectively bred stocks, the use of wild fish for producing fishmeal and oils for aquaculture feed. Besides, reproductive and health aspects, such as genetic pollution and disease transfers, are associated with these

issues. The aquaculture sector should be encouraged to develop and implement sustainable and environmentally friendly technologies to minimise impacts and to grow in a manner that is both economically and environmentally beneficial to European marine waters and coastal communities (EC, 2021b).

Reduce the feed footprint in aquaculture

The EU's Strategic Guidelines for a More Sustainable and Competitive EU Aquaculture for the Period 2021 to 2030 emphasise reducing the ecological footprint of feed as a priority for the sector (EC, 2021b). The challenge of sustainable feeds is approached from multiple angles through policies and regulations, standards, and targeted research programmes.

Under the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), the EU supports sustainable fishing practices, ensuring that fishmeal and fish oil are sourced responsibly for aquaculture. That said, EU policies should go beyond ensuring sustainably sourced wild fish for fish feed, as waste from fish processing should also be reduced, and feed alternatives should be used. By promoting alternative feed ingredients, the EU aims to protect wild fish populations and decrease overfishing, ensuring a more sustainable source of nutrients for farmed fish.

The European Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy both call for the sustainable use of natural resources, including aquaculture. These policies encourage reducing the environmental impacts of aquaculture feed production by supporting innovations and research into sustainable alternatives. For example, the EU supports the development of sustainable feed ingredients and alternatives through support for research into plant-based and novel ingredients to reduce the reliance on fishmeal and fish oil. Alternative, sustainable feed ingredient research is looking at insect protein, algae and seaweed, proteins derived from bacteria, yeast, fungi, legumes, oilseeds, and more. The EU is funding numerous research projects to develop new, more sustainable feed formulations. These projects explore the environmental and economic viability of alternative ingredients, focusing on reducing carbon and ecological footprints. Initiatives such as FEED-X work towards scaling up the production of sustainable feed alternatives across the EU, helping transition the industry towards more environmentally friendly feed options.

Improving feed efficiency is crucial to reducing the overall footprint of aquaculture. By optimising feed conversion ratios (FCRs) through better management practices and nutritional strategies, the sector can reduce the amount of feed needed for each kilogram of fish produced. Technologies such as “precision feeding” and automated feed systems are being developed and adopted to ensure that farmed fish receive the optimal amount of feed while minimising waste and environmental impact.

The EU's Farm to Fork Strategy emphasises the importance of a circular economy in aquaculture. The use of by-products from food processing industries (e.g., trimmings, offcuts) for feed is encouraged, reducing waste and the overall environmental impact. The EU-funded projects, such as [AQUAEXCEL3.0](#) and [BLUEBIOMED](#), work on innovative technologies that support the circular bioeconomy, including turning agricultural and fishery waste into feed ingredients for aquaculture.

The EU is also advancing transparency and traceability in aquaculture feed through policies and regulations (the CFP, together with the General Food Law (EC, 2002), digital tools, stricter regulations, and consumer-facing initiatives, ensuring sustainable and responsible feed sourcing.

The EU promotes sustainability through voluntary certifications and standards, such as the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) certification, which includes criteria related to sustainable feed sourcing.

European aquaculture producers are encouraged to meet these standards to ensure environmentally responsible operations, including feed use.

The EU is addressing the environmental and feed footprint of aquaculture through a combination of policy measures, research funding, and promoting innovation in feed alternatives. By focusing on sustainable ingredients, optimising feed use, and reducing reliance on wild fish stocks, the EU's policies, funding efforts, and strategies aim to reduce the pressure on wild fisheries as food for farmed fish and ensure long-term sustainability in the sector.

Prevention and management of escapees and interactions with wild fauna

Implementing measures to prevent and manage escapees of farmed species from aquaculture facilities and interactions with wild fauna (e.g., fish, birds, reptiles, marine mammals), as well as predator control, should be applied to minimise the risk of impact on ecosystem and biodiversity according to WFD and MSFD objectives (EC, 2000 and EC, 2008) and guiding elements of regional plans. Good practices include i) the adoption of technical standards for pen design, mooring systems and nets to reduce structural accidents, particularly in the case of exceptional marine weather events, which are expected to increase in climate change scenario: ii) the location of aquaculture farms to minimise the interactions with wild fauna and iii) develop and/or adopt codes of good practices or recommendations by aquaculture operators based on different farming systems, including contingency plans for the recovery of escapees, proper handling procedures for fish transfer, grading and harvest and routine preventive activities (e.g., maintenance of gears, check of containment units). The predator control system should attempt to minimise the impact on biodiversity and the predators themselves. It will depend on the location, the aquaculture system, the species and the life-stage being cultured. Reporting and increasing the transparency and access to data on both escapee events and lethal accidents to wild fauna should be implemented across aquaculture sectors.

Responsible use of non-native species

Aquaculture is an important vector of introduction of alien species in Europe's seas and is of pivotal importance in mitigating the risk of escapees and the irreversible impacts on fisheries, aquaculture stock and biodiversity (EC, 2007; ICES, 2012; EC, 2014).

At the EU level, Act 708/2007 (EC, 2007) is applied at different levels in the Member States, and risk assessment protocols, specific biosecurity plans, and measures for the traceability of introduction and translocation of target and non-target should be implemented. Considering the transboundary risk of spreading non-native (i.e., alien) species, pathogens and parasites, any introduction should be evaluated according to the environmental risk assessment and reported by MS. The use of non-native species in aquaculture should not be allowed when the environmental risk assessment is higher than "low" and the use of locally absent species should be controlled to reduce the risk of transfer of non-target organisms. Farming alien species in aquaculture facilities in direct contact with the surrounding environment (e.g., net pen systems) should be avoided, and escape prevention measures and contingency plans should be ready to reduce the risk associated with events of escapees. The introduction of non-target species associated with bivalve and algae introduction deserves particular attention (Di Blasio et al., 2023; Gozlan et al., 2024), also resulting in the most important pressure exerted by low trophic farming systems in Europe's seas (see Sankey diagram results, Regional assessments).

Implement biosecurity and disease prevention

The implementation of biosecurity plans and appropriate prophylaxis programs, as through the use of vaccines, will contribute to preventing and controlling the occurrence of diseases and reduce the use of pharmaceuticals, ensuring food security and minimising effects on the environment and biodiversity. The new Animal Health Law (Regulation 2016/429/EU) introduces a risk-based approach, prioritising prevention and good husbandry practices through the application of biosecurity measures and sanitary surveillance in aquaculture farming systems in a “One Health” perspective (Steniford et al., 2020). The biosecurity plans should be implemented considering farmed species, the typology of the culture system, the environmental conditions at the production site, and the dimensions and risks of interaction with wild fauna.

Responsible use of chemicals and pharmaceuticals

Veterinary medicines (antimicrobial and antiparasitic substances), biocides, antifoulants and feed additives commonly used to improve the survival, performance and quality of farmed species, particularly in intensive aquaculture rearing systems, should be applied based on regulatory provisions and follow a responsible approach, to minimise the risk of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and potential impacts on ecosystems. Developed guidance on environmental risk assessment and implementation of mitigation measures for the use of chemicals in aquaculture deal with Zero Pollution Action Plan (EC, 2021c), which includes, among targets, the reduction of 50% the sale of antimicrobials in aquaculture by 2030. Reducing the use of chemicals is also relevant for the achievement of environmental objectives set by WFD and MSFD (Descriptor 8) and matches with recommendations of international organisations (FAO, WHO, and WOAH). In the case of antibiotics, particular attention should be paid to those identified as critically important for human health by the World Health Organization (WHO). The Regulation 2021/16/EU laying down the necessary measures and practical arrangements for the Union database on veterinary medicinal products (EC, 2021d), together with supplementary and implementing regulations, will improve data collection and transparency on antibiotic use in aquaculture. Increasing the number of approved veterinary drugs for use in aquaculture is further needed, as it can contribute to reducing the likelihood of developing AMR.

Implementation of animal welfare practices

The welfare of farmed aquatic species is a key element of the multidimensional “One Health” approach applied to aquaculture for the health of humans, animals and the environment. The adoption of good animal welfare practices and standards responds to guiding elements and/or regulatory provisions for sustainable, responsible and ethical aquaculture that meets the expectations of society and consumers (EC, 2021b; UNEP, 2023). Ensuring environmental quality, respecting species-specific needs and considering different farming systems together with the adoption of proper fish handling procedures are essential to minimise stressful conditions and the risk of disease outbreaks in aquaculture (EU Platform on Animal Welfare - Own Initiative Group on Fish, 2022). The adoption of animal welfare management plans based on validated and verifiable Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs) should be encouraged (Noble et al., 2018; ISPRA, 2021). The use of innovative tools for real-time monitoring of environmental conditions, biomass, and animal health and behaviour further contributes to improved animal welfare and more sustainable aquaculture practices.

Reduction of plastic waste from aquaculture activities

Implementation of practices and technologies for plastic waste prevention and removal along the aquaculture production chain (e.g., farming, processing), promoting the use of durable, sustainable, recyclable or reusable components, biodegradable materials and minimising packaging waste. Actions should take into account the European Strategy for Plastics in the Circular Economy and the legal framework (EC, 2018; EC, 2019b; EC, 2019c), as well as regional (e.g., UNEP, 2023) and/or national plans on marine litter which include the aquaculture sector. The application of Best Available Technology (BAT) and Best Environmental Practice (BEP), such as appropriate equipment design and materials, waste handling practices, and maintenance and repair of gears, should be further implemented by aquaculture producers (HELCOM, 2023).

Best placement for marine aquaculture sites

Marine spatial plans address space for marine aquaculture. By implementing the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSP, Directive 2014/89/EU), the EU asked MS to implement planning and zoning tools for their maritime areas and aims to ensure that aquaculture has a space in the Member States' plans and contributing to sustainable development (Chapela et al., 2022). Based on the MSP methodology and framework, marine aquaculture activities are to be sited based on habitat constraints, environmental conditions and the carrying capacity of the system. Non-EU Member States use MSP in their national plans for the area planning of aquaculture activities in the coastal zones (Planning and Building Act of 2008, Norway).

The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2021) also highlights the importance of leveraging nature-based solutions, including sustainable aquaculture, to enhance biodiversity within these designated zones. By promoting the integration of aquaculture activities, e.g., shellfish farming into Natura 2000 areas, valuable ecosystem services can be provided by the aquaculture activities to the Natura 2000 areas.

The Water Framework Directive (EC, 2000) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (EC, 2008), together with the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive (EC, 2001) and the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive (EC, 2011) are the main environmental regulatory tools, implemented through national legislation, for ensuring the environmental sustainability of aquaculture.

Aquaculture activities can potentially affect aquatic ecosystems, for example through the introduction of non-indigenous species (NIS), transmission of infectious diseases, nutrients, organic matter, contaminants, litter, disturbance to wildlife, and escapees, with implications for several MSFD descriptors: biodiversity (D1), non-indigenous species (D2), commercial fish and shellfish (D3), food webs (D4), eutrophication (D5), seafloor integrity (D6), hydrographic conditions (D7), contaminants (D8), fish and seafood contaminants (D9), marine litter (D10) and energy including underwater noise (D11). To control and reduce potential impacts from aquaculture, site-specific environmental monitoring programmes should be adopted and implemented, taking into consideration the carrying capacity of the site, the farming systems, location, cultured species and biomass, and the characteristics and sensitivity or vulnerability of the environment. Different indicators should be applied to address the sediment, water column, and biota (benthic and/or pelagic biodiversity composition and structure), as well as escape events and lethal incidents of endangered species. Where possible, the concepts of mixing zone and “Allowable of Effects” (AZE) should be further applied (UNEP, 2023).

Administrations should facilitate the aquaculture sector in the process of licensing and monitoring, providing clear information on the typology of parameters or data that should be provided, as well as the quality and quantity of the information required.

Currently, the Data Collection Framework (DCF) under the Common Fisheries Policy contains provisions requiring Member States to collect and transmit to end-users socio-economic data on marine aquaculture but does not cover data on the environmental performance of the aquaculture sector. Such data is needed to better assess policy options to support the sustainable development of aquaculture and should be readily available at the EU level. The adoption of regional technical standards across the sector may help to mitigate environmental impacts across a range of aquaculture systems and species. Member States and the industry are encouraged to implement good aquaculture practices, demonstrating the complementarity between environmental protection and sustainable aquaculture and its contribution to the green transition and blue economy (EC, 2021).

Farming low trophic species

The practice of farming low-trophic species is supported by several EU policies and practices. The EU Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy advocates for sustainable practices and the promotion of aquaculture for low-trophic species under the EU Green Deal (EC, 2020). The Food from Oceans Report emphasises the importance of low-trophic aquaculture, focusing on species like algae and the adoption of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (EC, 2017). Further, low trophic species like oysters, mussels, and clams provide regulating services to the ecosystem as these species remove excess nutrients, particulates, and contaminants from the water. The cultivation of algae contributes to carbon sequestration as algae absorb carbon dioxide through photosynthesis. The EU Blue Growth Strategy encourages the sustainable development of maritime sectors, including aquaculture, to foster economic growth while protecting marine ecosystems. Adopting integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) in the future might enhance resource efficiency and reduce environmental impacts in alignment with the EU Blue Growth Strategy.

Farming low-trophic species not only supports sustainable aquaculture but also plays a key role in protecting and enhancing biodiversity within marine protected areas. The Natura 2000 network aims to protect the natural areas and species in the European Union. Integrating sustainable aquaculture activities, such as farming low-trophic species, into Natura 2000 areas can positively impact local biodiversity through water filtration, habitat creation, and the provision of nursery and spawning grounds, aligning with the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (Bridger et al., 2024; EC, 2021).

3.5 Transversal

Climate change mitigation and adaptation

There are clear signs of changes in the oceans globally. Ocean warming (0.88°C higher in 2011-2020 compared to 1850-1900), oxygen loss (down 3-4% by 2100) and ocean acidification (decreased pH by 30% in 2023 compared to 1700) may be occurring at a speed that may be too fast for species to adapt to the changes. According to the EEA, Europe's marine areas and marine life are unequally vulnerable to climate change, and this driver may account for up to half of the combined impacts on marine ecosystems (EEA, 2024).

Such a process affects Europe's marine ecosystems and may reflect on several effects, including heat waves and mass mortalities, and the displacement of species favouring the expansion towards the north of warm species (Baudron et al., 2020). This is the case of warm-favouring species in the Greater North and Celtic

Seas, which have increased and are positively correlated with recent past sea surface temperatures (EEA, 2024). A similar pattern has been observed in the Mediterranean Sea, where processes such as meridionalisation (the northward spread of species of warm-temperature affinity) and tropicalisation (the northward expansion of alien species of tropical affinity) of the biotic communities have been detected (Tsikliras et al., 2014; Fortibuoni et al., 2015; Azzurro et al., 2019).

In particular, semi-enclosed seas — such as the Baltic Sea and the Adriatic Sea — and shallow coastal areas are more vulnerable to climate change compared to deeper, offshore areas. Bottom-living communities and fish are more vulnerable than highly mobile mammals and birds, for example. This potentially impacts the whole marine food web and dependent fisheries.

Indeed, the fisheries sector is highly vulnerable to climate change, given its potential effect on stock biomass and spatial distribution, which in turn affects fishing catches and strategies (Payne et al., 2021; Hidalgo et al., 2022). A series of adaptive management strategies and measures (see Bahri et al., 2021), if properly implemented, have the potential to allow coping with such new emerging (and partially unpredictable) conditions, as detailed below.

Adaptive Management Strategies

- Develop adaptive management frameworks that can quickly respond to changing environmental conditions and shifting fish populations due to climate change. Such a framework should include knowledge of climate effects in stock assessment and forecasts. Re-evaluate stock boundaries and data collection systems whenever a mismatch arises from changing climate affecting the stock distribution and timing of biological processes, natural mortality rates, invasive species, etc. (i.e., a flexible monitoring and management system). Adaptation of harvest control rules according to new conditions is also needed, including adapting quotas where relevant.

- Facing uncertainties in future climate, developing impact assessment in a scenario-based framework for testing the sensitivity to ecological and economic effects arising from environmental changes induced by climate change under current management measures is a way forward (e.g., Bastardie et al., 2022). This further includes conducting scenario planning to anticipate and prepare for the potential impacts of climate change on fisheries and aquaculture and implement dedicated adaptation strategies addressing different fisheries and aquaculture sectors specifically. A vulnerability assessment shall allow priority fisheries and aquaculture sectors that present high vulnerability potential to climate change to be identified, thus allowing them to prioritise adaptation measures.

- Promote innovation to reduce carbon use and reach carbon neutrality and energy-efficient practices, including the use and production of renewable energy in fishing and aquaculture operations to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, support the development and uptake of green fuels to power fishing vessels, and support carbon-neutral aquaculture practices.

- Support initiatives that enhance carbon sequestration in marine ecosystems, such as the protection and restoration of blue carbon habitats like seagrasses and mangroves (see restoration section).

Resilient aquaculture systems

Climate change is expected to affect food security and the sustainability of the aquaculture sector. The vulnerability of aquaculture to climate change depends on several factors, including the geographical location of production sites, production systems, species, and farming environments (Cubillo et al., 2021; Falconer et al., 2022). Extreme weather events can severely damage aquaculture infrastructure, causing massive escapes and product loss with significant economic impacts. Heat waves lead to prolonged and

severe hypoxia and algal blooms, especially in coastal and transitional waters, causing stress, microbial pollution and mortality events in farmed species. Changes in environmental conditions following climate change can further favour the spread of alien species and pathogens affecting aquaculture performance, animal health and food safety. Sea level rise further leads to increased salinity and habitat loss in estuarine environments, affecting local aquaculture activities. Effective and long-lasting adaptation strategies are needed (EEA, 2019) and include: i) development of ad hoc climate change impact indicators for aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean areas; ii) development of marine spatial plans for aquaculture in a climate change scenario; iii) encourage the diversification of aquaculture species and systems to increase resilience to climate change impacts; iv) selective breeding of climate-resilient species; v) innovative tools and technologies to predict and cope with extreme events.

The future of aquaculture lies in building resilience through the diversification of species and the development of climate-adaptive aquaculture practices. By fostering selective breeding programs and expanding the use of sustainable and adaptable species, the aquaculture industry can better navigate the uncertainties posed by climate change while continuing to meet global seafood demands sustainably.

- Diversify cultured species and systems to increase resilience to climate change impacts. Encouraging the diversification of aquaculture species and systems is a vital strategy to bolster resilience against these threats. Species diversification, particularly the expansion of polyculture systems, integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA), and a shift towards low trophic-level species, can help mitigate the effects of environmental changes. For example, shellfish like mussels and seaweed in IMTA systems can benefit from nutrient recycling, contributing to overall ecosystem health while also serving as low-energy, resilient food sources (ICES, 2024).

Climate change poses significant challenges to species currently farmed, such as Atlantic salmon, European sea bass, and gilthead sea bream, which are sensitive to higher temperatures. In regions like southern Portugal, increased water temperatures can exceed the reproductive thresholds of certain finfish species, resulting in stress, reduced oxygen levels, and degraded water quality, which in turn heightens disease risks. Shellfish aquaculture, which relies heavily on natural seed settlement, faces threats from elevated temperatures, harmful algal blooms (HABs), and changes in pH due to ocean acidification. These conditions can lead to slower growth rates, increased mortality, and diminished productivity, particularly for shell-forming organisms like oysters and mussels.

To address these challenges, investing in selective breeding programs to develop climate-resilient aquaculture species is critical. Breeding species that can tolerate higher temperatures, fluctuations in salinity, and lower oxygen levels would reduce vulnerability to climate-induced stressors. Selective breeding for disease resistance can also help mitigate the increased risk of pathogens associated with warming waters. For instance, genetic improvements in shellfish that enhance their ability to withstand acidic conditions or reduce the accumulation of toxins from HABs can help stabilise production levels even as environmental conditions shift. Moreover, breeding efforts can extend to finfish species to develop more thermally tolerant strains that can continue to thrive in warmer waters.

Community and stakeholder engagement

As the fisheries and aquaculture sectors face multiple challenges besides the overexploitation issue, tackling them in an ecosystem approach requires stakeholder engagement, community arrangement to access new funding (for gear modification, retrofitting, innovation) and renewal of the working force; for example, achieving EU targets for decarbonising the fishing sector and reaching a carbon-neutral industry by 2050. Such effort will require implementing existing technological solutions, support from R&D for developing new innovative ones, and avoiding often-neglected indirect sectoral impacts such as GHG

emissions induced by energy use and habitat degradation such as affecting the blue carbon habitats. Hence, helpful support will include:

- Conducting training programs for fishers and aquaculture farmers on sustainable practices, climate change adaptation, and habitat conservation.
- Launching awareness campaigns to educate communities and stakeholders about the importance of sustainable fisheries and aquaculture.
- Improving the social acceptance of aquaculture by ensuring transparency and early involvement of stakeholders in aquaculture planning and promoting synergies with other marine activities.
- Developing stakeholder engagement strategies that outline the key principles of stakeholder engagement and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders (ICES, 2023).
- Organising workshops and meetings to consult stakeholders on knowledge needs, methods, data, and their expert knowledge to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration.
- Incorporating expert knowledge into the scientific and evidence basis that supports management decisions.

Co-management approaches

Co-management and results-based management systems put the focus on the local communities of stakeholders, for example, to develop new gear types that will avoid unwanted catches ([Alzorriz et al., 2016](#)) or lower impact aquaculture systems. Co-management or participatory approaches could help for better compliance ([Röckmann et al., 2012](#)) by increasing the mutual trust between the local communities and the public administration and preventing the imposition of issues for conservation only ([Ramírez-Monsalve et al., 2016](#); [Maya Jariago et al., 2018](#)). It should also promote the involvement of small-scale fishermen that are typically poorly organised. The “co-designing” of management means that the measures are developed together with and reviewed by scientists. The different living experiences at sea, possible participation in previous projects, comparisons with different case studies, etc., all make the perception of the overexploitation and marine habitat degradation issue vary among different stakeholders. Promoting awareness, ocean literacy, and a common understanding are also key in incentivising the sectors to change mindsets. Hence, helpful support will include:

- Promoting co-management approaches that involve local communities, fishermen, aquaculture farmers, and other stakeholders in the decision-making process to ensure that management measures are locally appropriate and supported. This could also include a derogation of power from the central/local administration to fishermen or their organisations, who would take a leading role in the co-management of a given resource (Raicevich et al., 2018). Such a process shall be accompanied by a series of rules to control the actual implementation of the co-management measures. Such collaboration between governments, NGOs, and the private sector can be further promoted to implement joint projects and share resources for sustainable management.

- Promoting knowledge co-creation. In order to increase the legitimacy, credibility, and saliency of science in support of fisheries management, the engagement of stakeholders in the co-creation with the scientists on the knowledge base for fisheries management is crucial. Such an approach, as witnessed in several research projects and real case studies (Holm et al., 2020), shows that the inclusion of fishermen's ecological knowledge in both the creation of science and the definition of possible management approaches greatly enhances the likelihood of the improved participation of fishermen into management and respect of the rules.

- Enhancing innovation, social learning, and ocean literacy through knowledge exchange and collaboration to address operational, tactical, and strategic challenges.

Monitoring and data collection

The demand for data is growing in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors as data demand for stock assessment is incremented by data requests to characterise the marine environment and the multifaceted impacts of fisheries and aquaculture sectors, from species to habitats and ecosystems.

This determines a need for enhanced monitoring programs by continuing to collect robust empirical data to underpin any studies and subsequent modelling that are eventually used to provide advice, both on resource and environmental status. Regarding stock assessment, scientists warn that we should limit management advice based on the outputs of models that use modelled data as input. This comes with developing indicators issued from assessment studies.

Monitoring deals with different scales to acquire data that require different instrumentations and protocols, including:

- Remote Electronic Monitoring (REM): involves technologies like CCTV cameras on fishing vessels to monitor catches on bycatch, compliance with the landing obligation and other regulations.
- Electronic reporting systems: Electronic reporting of all catches to improve the traceability of fisheries products, including real-time data.
- Tracking of fishing vessels: enhanced tracking systems using vessel position data (e.g., VMS, AIS) and other geospatial data to monitor the activities of all fishing vessels, including small-scale fisheries and aquaculture activities.
- Optimising monitoring programmes fostering synergies and integration between data collection programmes under environmental and fisheries policies (e.g., MSFD, HD, WFD and CFP).
- Developing guidance for data collection and reporting and identifying common environmental indicators to monitor the environmental performance of fisheries and aquaculture.
- Continuing supporting oceanographic research & monitoring and mapping seabed habitats to understand pressure-impact relationships and provide an accurate mapping for maritime spatial planning and habitat protection.
- - Encouraging citizen science initiatives where local communities and fishermen contribute to data collection and monitoring efforts.

Table 3-2 provides a non-exhaustive list of the main legal instruments and funding mechanisms associated with these EU/regional monitoring programmes.

Research and development (R&D)

Knowledge and integration are supported by R&D alongside the collection of harmonised, reliable, and accurate data sets, furthering the need for an ecosystem approach beyond considering standard fisheries or aquaculture-related science only. In this context, R&D plays a major role in supporting tactical solutions (e.g., innovation in processes) and strategic understanding of key elements for achieving sustainability of human uses of marine resources and its environment. This includes developing research efforts to:

- Improve understanding of marine ecosystems, fish population dynamics, and the cumulative impacts of climate change and other human-induced pressures. This includes research in support of the implementation of an Ecosystem-based approach to ensure marine ecosystems are

managed within their biological boundaries and in the light of ensuring their resilience, providing tools for assessment and models for predicting the role of human pressures on the environmental status in an integrative manner.

- Provide grants and funding opportunities for innovative projects and technologies that enhance the sustainability of fisheries and aquaculture. This includes, for instance, the development of technical solutions for the development of selective fishing gear that can reduce bycatch or minimise the impact on benthic habitats and communities, thus fostering a technological transition towards more sustainable fisheries. Such an approach should consider not only technological innovation in fishing gear and technology but also technical innovation along the whole value chain (e.g., for reducing CO₂ footprint).
- Ensure support with a data warehouse. For example, the EU Copernicus Marine Data Store presents one of the largest data inventories of high-quality ocean data for near real-time hindcasts, observations, forecasts, satellite and in-situ observations, re-analysis, etc. (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/>). Copernicus Marine Service provides data from satellites, in-situ sensors, and numerical models covering the global ocean. Copernicus also provides information on past, present, and future trends, which are made available to empower all users who want to drive the blue economy, as well as scientific innovation and support sustainable ocean initiatives. Copernicus handles all types of environmental variables, including global ocean variables and monitoring indicators. Another example is given by ICES, which is the organisation in charge of fisheries- and aquaculture-related and linked marine science data. By maximising the availability of data to the community at large, ICES promotes the use of these data, thereby ensuring that their maximum value can be realised and thus contribute to an increased understanding of the marine environment. These data can be found at the ICES marine data centre: <https://www.ices.dk/data/data-portals/Pages/default.aspx>.

Reforming harmful subsidies

Well-designed subsidies and government support can play a crucial role in maintaining healthy fish stocks and ecosystems, increasing fish stock productivity, and building resilience within the fisheries sector. However, poorly targeted subsidies risk promoting unsustainable fishing and aquaculture practices (OECD, 2023).

The primary financial instrument under the CFP for 2021-2027 is the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)¹ (EC, 2021e), with a total budget of €6.108 billion. EMFAF is structured around four priorities aimed at fostering long-term environmental, economic, and social sustainability within the EU. While the EU has made some progress in reforming subsidies capacity-enhancing subsidies persist, undermining international commitments² and further jeopardising the transition to sustainable fisheries (Skerritt et al., 2020; Brenne et al. 2021; Villasante et al., 2022). Ensuring that subsidies meet their intended outcomes is also essential. For instance, the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF), EMFAF's predecessor, also funded innovations in selective fishing gear to reduce bycatch, yet incidental catches of sensitive species remain a major threat (ECA, 2020).

¹ Previous programmes: (1) Financial Instrument for Fisheries Guidance - FIFG (1994-1999); (2) FIFG (2000–2006) ([Council of the EU, 1993](#)), (3) European Fisheries Fund (EFF, 2007–2013) ([Council of the EU, 2006](#); [European Commission, 2007](#)), and (4) European Maritime and Fisheries Fund EMFF (2014–2020) ([European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2014](#))

² Such as for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in particular, SDG target 14.6 demanded to, "by 2020, prohibit certain forms of fisheries subsidies which contribute to overcapacity and overfishing [...] and refrain from introducing new such subsidies"

Besides the EMFAF, the EU fisheries sector benefits from public support through fishing access agreements with third countries under the CFP's external dimension, including the Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs). An [evaluation](#) of the SFPAs between 2015 and 2020, showed that annual spending for these agreements averaged €159 million, with 33% benefiting the local fishing sector but only 2% directed towards ecosystem protection initiatives.

Additionally, the sector benefits from indirect subsidies, such as fuel tax exemptions, and Member States can supplement EU support within their own national budgets (e.g. State and sub-State aids). Such subsidies, in particular fuel tax exemptions, allow unsustainable and unviable activities to continue, contributing to overcapacity, overfishing and climate change impacts (Carvalho and Guillen, 2021). Redirecting these funds to invest more in sustainable fisheries management and enforcement or toward alternatives, such as lower income tax to improve the welfare of fishermen or fleet decarbonisation efforts, could reduce negative environmental impacts while aligning with the EGD's goal of climate neutrality by 2050 and the goal of ending harmful fisheries subsidies.

The EU's ongoing Energy Taxation Directive ([ETD](#)) revision offers an opportunity to remove fuel tax exemptions. Due to tax exemptions, fishers pay less for fuel than the general public. This reduces the costs of fishing, potentially leading to an increase of fishing capacity and contributing to overfishing. Setting higher minimum tax rates than those currently proposed under the ETD review, which are widely considered too low to support the EU's climate objectives, would help remove incentives for overconsumption.

At the international level, the World Trade Organization (WTO) reached a landmark agreement in 2022 to prohibit some of the most harmful types of fisheries subsidies, including those that benefit illegal, unreported and unregulated (IUU) fishing. While this agreement is a significant milestone in reducing harmful subsidies, further negotiations are needed to address subsidies that contribute to overcapacity and overfishing. The WTO agreement will take effect only once two-thirds of its 164 members formally ratify it, a process that is still ongoing. By aligning its own subsidies and regulatory frameworks, the EU can set an example for effective, sustainable fisheries management. The EU could also support the WTO agreement by advocating for rigorous reporting standards to ensure transparency, encouraging major subsidising countries, including EU Member States, to commit to sustainability goals.

Table 3-2 Main legal frameworks and associated monitoring programmes towards the transition objectives in Table 3-1.

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
EU Policies					
DG MARE					
Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)	EU Data Collection Framework Regulation (DCF)	Scientific Research and Data Collection	EU Multiannual programs for data collection (MAP) Mandatory research surveys at sea	DG Joint Research Centre (JRC)	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) reports and scientific advice
	Technical Measures Regulation (TMR) Contribute to the objectives of the CFP, MSFD (GES) and Nature Directives	Environmental Sustainability	Data calls	STECF Data dissemination	STECF EWG and reports Technical measures Commission reports
	Control regulation. Includes monitoring programmes for tracking commercial fishing vessels (VMS, geospatial data), electronic catch reporting, product traceability and recreational fisheries reporting	Governance and Policy Frameworks	EU Operations ICES (vessel monitoring system VMS)	European Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA), ICES (VMS)	EFCA Fisheries Information System Joint Deployment Plans

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
	EU fleet register Reference database for vessels characteristics	Governance and Policy Frameworks	EU fleet register database	DG MARE	EU fleet ceilings Fleet Register (europa. eu) EU fleet at a glance Fleet Register (europa. eu)
	Advisory Councils (AC) Contribute to fisheries and aquaculture management and conservation measures	Governance and Policy Frameworks	Aquaculture AC , Baltic Sea AC , Black Sea AC , Long Distance AC , Market AC , Mediterranean Sea AC , North Sea AC , North-western waters AC , Outermost regions AC , Pelagic stocks AC , South-western waters AC		European Atlas of the Seas
	Common Market Organisation (CMO) strengthens the role of the actors on the ground: consumers receive information on the products sold on the EU market, and operators apply the same rules, regardless of the origin of the product	Social Responsibility	Information on Seafood Markets Marketing standards Consumer information Market intelligence (EUMOFA) Producer Organisations_	DG MARE	European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products EUMOFA database and dashboards Market overviews and publications
Multiannual financial framework	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)	Economic Viability	Common (output and result) indicators and core performance indicators	FAMENET , Infosys	Monitoring and evaluation
Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD)	Co-existence and multi-use	Governance and Policy Frameworks	Support the EU Integrated Maritime Policy	MSP Platform	National MSPs Commission Progress report

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
EU Regulation Framework on the use of Alien and locally absent species in Aquaculture Reg. 708/2007	Risk assessment for introduction of alien species for aquaculture purpose	Governance and Policy Frameworks	Support invasive alien species regulation and MSFD	EU DC aquaculture Registers of introduction	MS registers
DG ENV					
Water Framework Directive (WFD)	Good chemical and ecological status (GES)	Environmental Sustainability	River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) and Programmes of Measures (PoMs)	EEA WISE-Freshwater	State of water
Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)	Good environmental status (GES)	Environmental Sustainability	Aggregated data for the 11 marine descriptors	EEA WISE-Marine	State of Europe's seas
Birds Directive (BD)	Natura 2000 network of protected areas (SPAs)	Environmental Sustainability	Support the designation and management of Natura 2000 sites	EEA BISE	State of nature
Habitats Directive (HD)	Natura 2000 network of protected areas (SCIs/SACs)	Environmental Sustainability			
8th Environment Action Programme (EAP)	Monitor progress towards the EU's environment and climate goals to 2030, as well as the 2050 long-term vision to 'live well, within planetary boundaries	Environmental Sustainability	Headline indicators	EEA ECHA	Monitoring reports on progress towards the 8th EAP objectives (2023 edition) EEA / 8th EAP - indicator-based progress

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
Nature Restoration Law (NRL)	Restore degraded ecosystems	Environmental Sustainability	MS data submission by mid-2026	EEA	National Restoration Plans, progress on targets
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive (EIA)	Evaluate the effects of public and private projects on the environment	Environmental Sustainability	Environmental impact assessment of projects	DG ENV	Implementation report
Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA)	Evaluate the effects of certain plans and programmes on the environment	Environmental Sustainability	Environmental assessment of certain plans and programmes	DG ENV	National summaries
Invasive Alien Species Regulation (IAS)	Prevent and minimise the effects of invasive alien species on Europe's biodiversity	Environmental Sustainability	European Alien Species Information Network EASIN	DG JRC	European Red List of Species Commission reports
Single-use Plastics Directive (SUP)	Support the MSFD, ZPAP and CEAP - Reduce marine litter	Environmental Sustainability	Marine litter assessment tool (MALT)	DG JRC EMODNET	EEA data reporting and assessment
DG RTD					
Framework Programme	Research and innovation funding programme until 2027 Horizon Europe	Scientific Research and Data Collection	Dashboards	CINEA	Horizon Europe programme analysis and outline of the monitoring approach
Cross-cutting DG ENV, CLIMA, ENER					

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
LIFE Programme	Funding instrument for Climate action, environment and nature protection	Scientific Research and Data Collection	LIFE public dashboard	CINEA	Project database
Eurostat Fisheries and aquaculture	Data collection	Scientific Research and Data Collection	Databases	EC	Publications
Copernicus Programme	Information services from satellite Earth Observation and in-situ (non-space) data	Scientific Research and Data Collection	satellite and in-situ data Data and products (marine)	EC	Copernicus Marine services
Other					
Marine Litter Watch (MLW)	Citizen-based app to help fill data gaps in beach litter monitoring required by the MSFD	Social Responsibility	MLW App!	EEA	Publications
Regional and international					
International organisations					
International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)	Coordinated surveys to monitor and assess marine ecosystems and fisheries. Science development and advisory services.	Scientific Research and Data Collection	ICES data calls and tools	ICES	ICES marine data

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO)	Fisheries Global Information System (FIGIS) Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System (FIRMS) Integrated web-based dissemination system	Governance and Policy Frameworks	FIRMS Stocks and Fisheries Map Viewer (fao.org) FishStat FishInfo	FAO	FAO Committee on Fisheries (COFI) The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture (SOFA)
Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development Fisheries and Aquaculture (OECD)		Governance and Policy Frameworks	OECD Committee for Fisheries (COFI) Data Explorer Fisheries and aquaculture data Fisheries Support Estimate (FSE) database	OECD	OECD Review of Fisheries (2022)
International Maritime Organisation (IMO)	Monitoring IMO-BWM International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast Water and Sediments	Governance and Policy Frameworks	IMO Information Facts and figures	IMO	Marine Environment
Regional Seas Conventions (RSCs)					
Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM)	Monitoring programmes	Environmental Sustainability	Databases and maps	HELCOM	Baltic Sea Action Plan Holistic Assessments (HOLAS)
Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of	Coordinated Environmental Monitoring Programme (CEMP),	Environmental Sustainability	Data & Information Management System	OSPAR	Assessment Portal Quality Status Reports (QSR)

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
the NorthEast Atlantic (OSPAR)	Joint Assessment and Monitoring Programme (JAMP)				
Barcelona Convention (BC)	Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme (IMAP)	Environmental Sustainability	INFOMAP SYSTEM	UNEP/MAP	Mediterranean Action Plan (MAP) MED QSR
Bucharest Convention (BSC)	Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme (BSIMAP)	Environmental Sustainability	-	Black Sea Convention	-
Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs) (North Atlantic area only)					
General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM)	Monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS)	Scientific Research and Data Collection	Databases Data Collection Reference Framework (GFCM)	FAO GFCM	The State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries (SoMFj)
International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT)	Monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS)	Scientific Research and Data Collection	ICCAT statistical databases	ICCAT	Management strategy evaluation (MSE)
Northeast Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC)	Monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS)	Scientific Research and Data Collection	Catch Statistics -	NEAFC	Compliance reports -

Legislative framework	Monitoring programme/scope	Main transition objective	Data collection	Data host/ location	Assessments
Northeast Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NAFO)	Monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS)	Scientific Research and Data Collection	Data and Statistics (STATLANT)	NAFO	Annual reports
North Atlantic Salmon Conservation Organization (NASCO)		Scientific Research and Data Collection	Catch Statistics	NASCO	-

4 Towards assessing the performance of existing measures

Key messages

- 1. Evaluating the effectiveness of current measures for sustainable fisheries and aquaculture:** This section introduces a preliminary framework for assessing the effectiveness of existing measures to manage fisheries and aquaculture, based on the HELCOM Sufficiency of Measures (SoM) methodology. This approach identifies whether current measures are sufficient to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) and highlights areas where measures may need to be upscaled or supplemented to meet sustainability goals.
- 2. Stepwise SoM analysis for projecting future needs:** The SoM analysis applies a structured, step-by-step methodology to evaluate the performance of implemented measures over time, considering natural time lags and projected activity levels. By comparing the "business-as-usual" (BAU) status with the environmental target (GES), this approach helps determine whether current efforts are adequate and where additional actions are necessary.
- 3. Expert engagement for comprehensive evaluation:** The analysis incorporates insights from expert groups to classify and assess the sufficiency of current measures. This collaborative process enhances the accuracy and relevance of evaluations, informing future adjustments in policies and management practices for fisheries and aquaculture.
- 4. Customised measures for fisheries and aquaculture impact reduction:** Tailored categories of measures, such as input and output controls, alternative governance instruments, and environmental restoration, are used to classify current actions targeting fisheries and aquaculture impacts. This approach allows for more precise targeting of efforts to manage pressures such as nutrient discharge, habitat degradation, bycatch, and pollution, supporting sustainable practices across marine regions.

This section explores a potential approach to assess the performance of existing measures and how these may need to be either upscaled (implementation, enforcement, incentives, etc.) or complemented with new measures to achieve objectives. It builds on HELCOM's Sufficiency of Measures (SoM) methodology to provide a framework for analysing the sufficiency of existing measures for fisheries and aquaculture at regional/subregional levels across Europe's seas.

4.1 Brief introduction to the Sufficiency of Measures (SoM) analysis

The Sufficiency of Measures (SoM) aims to assess the improvements in the environmental status and pressures achieved with existing measures and to inform whether these measures are sufficient to achieve the environmental target (i.e., the good environmental status (GES)) in the Baltic Sea by 2020-2035. It was developed by HELCOM to analyse the sufficiency of measures in the Baltic Sea to support the Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP) and the identification of new measures (Helcom, 2024).

The analysis provides an estimate of the status of the marine environment at a future point in time, considering the existing measures, their implementation, natural time-lags and a modelled development of the activity and pressure over this time period. This is referred to as the 'business-as-usual status (BAU)'. The comparison between the environmental target, i.e., GES, and the BAU state determines the sufficiency of the existing measures to achieve the target and the need to adopt additional measures.

The different elements of the SOM analysis and the links between them are shown in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1 Components of the SOM analysis, HELCOM/ACTION project. The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM), Helsinki, Finland. <https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-action-plan/som/>.

Data source: HELCOM 2024. HELCOM/ACTION project. The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM), Helsinki, Finland [Accessed on 1 September 2024]. Available at: <https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-action-plan/som/>. Licence: CC-BY-4.0.

The analysis is performed in 8 steps:

1. The first step is to identify the existing measures and group them into types. Measure types are used in the evaluation of the effect of measures in reducing the pressure (step 4).
2. Estimation of the time lag between measure and pressure needs to be estimated as even fully implemented measures do not have an immediate effect.
3. Link activity to pressure by expert judgement.
4. Estimation of effects of the measures in reducing pressures from activities by existing literature and expert judgement (online surveys).
5. Projected development of human activities/pressures under two alternative assumptions: no change or change in activity/pressure.
6. Linking reduced pressure with state components via surveys to experts that evaluate the impact of reducing pressures on specific state components linked to indicators or ecosystem components.
7. Comparison of BAU and GES and assessing sufficiency of measures.
8. Time lags in state recovery to evaluate the effect of the reduction of pressures separate from pressure-state.

Figure 4-2 Structure of the SOM analysis. The steps initiated in this report are coloured and in continuous arrows. Adapted from the HELCOM/ACTION project, The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM), Helsinki, Finland. <https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-action-plan/som/>.

Data source: HELCOM 2024. HELCOM/ACTION project. The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM), Helsinki, Finland [Accessed on 1 September 2024]. Available at: <https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-action-plan/som/>. Licence: CC-BY-4.0.

For a more detailed description of the analysis, including assumptions and limitations, please see [SOM approach.pdf \(helcom.fi\)](#).

4.2 Design of the analysis – Adapting the SoM approach

We followed the stepwise approach developed by the HELCOM/ACTION project. For the present report, only the first and third steps of the SOM analysis described above have been addressed (see Figure 4-2):

Step 1 – Identify existing measures

Existing measures refer to those that have been implemented, are currently being implemented or are planned to be implemented within the timeframe of the analysis (i.e., until 2024).

A preliminary list of groups of measures tailored to fisheries and aquaculture, initially compiled and provided by the HELCOM Secretariat, was used as the starting point from which to adapt the list to our analysis (Table 4-1 and Table 4-2).

These measure groups include: (1) “Input controls” - management measures that influence the amount of human activity that is permitted; (2). “Output controls” - direct limits on the amount and sizes of fish coming out of a fishery, and are standard management measures in the EU and worldwide; (3) “Alternative governance and economic instruments” - measures that account for the opinion that we are not managing fish stocks or ecosystems but fishermen; therefore, human behaviour and what influences human behaviour are entry points for management, and (4) “Environmental restoration and enhancement” - management tools that guide human activities in restoring damaged components of marine ecosystems.

The list of measure groups will be used to classify the measures reported by the experts in response to an online survey distributed to the European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) and other expert groups. (see Annex 2)

The European Environment Information and Observation Network (Eionet) is a partnership network of the [European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#) and its 38 member and cooperating countries. The EEA and Eionet gather and develop data and knowledge to support policymakers about Europe's environment. Taking advantage of this network, the aim is to request members of the relevant EIONET thematic groups to complete the survey on the measures addressing fisheries and aquaculture currently in place in EEA member countries.

While an attempt was made to engage with experts from the EIONET TG Marine and Oceans and the Food Systems Group to present the SoM methodology and introduce the survey, the response was limited. This exercise will again be undertaken in 2025, targeting not only EIONET TGs but also other relevant national experts. Once a relevant number of responses is available, we will continue with the following steps of the analysis (see Figure 4-2).

Step 3 - Link activity to pressure by expert judgement

The link between activities and pressure is developed using the approach and tools developed for the ICES ecosystem overviews and further developed in the fisheries and aquaculture regional assessments (see 2.1 and ICES 2023b).

Ultimately, the projected development of human activities/pressures will be used to anticipate the future paths of human activities and pressures under various scenarios of societal and economic changes. This involves comparing these projections against a "Business as Usual" scenario and assessing whether the measures being taken help in bridging the gap towards achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) even under these different scenarios.

Table 4-1 Preliminary list of groups of measures for fisheries.

Input measures (capacity and effort restrictions, technical measures)	Inshore/offshore seasonal/real-time and/or spatial closures
	Technical measures to reduce catches of unwanted species (bycatch reduction devices, etc.)
	Technical measures to reduce catches of unwanted sizes of fish (mesh size changes, sorting grids, etc.)
	Measures to reduce inshore/offshore commercial fishing capacity
	Unspecified MPA fisheries restrictions
Output measures (TAC controls, landing size controls, discard bans, bag limits)	Offshore/inshore catches of commercial fish in line with targets for MSY (TAC controls)
	CFP multi-annual plans for setting the catch or fishing effort limits
	EU/National species management plans (EU salmon discard plan, etc.)
	Inspection campaigns to reduce illegal fishing
Alternative governance and economic instruments (ecosystem approach, co-management, ecosystem services, tradable fishing concessions)	Ensure compliance with existing regulations (commercial and/or recreational)
	Promotion of sustainable fisheries (commercial and/or recreational)
	Eco-friendly vessels (low impact, low carbon vessels)
Environmental restoration and enhancement (artificial reefs, fishing aggregation device (FAD) management, etc.)	Ensure minimum ecological flow, e.g., river dam removal and application of the best available solution for fish passage on existing obstructions (salmon, sea trout, eel)
	Coastal species management plans
	Shallow coastal habitat restoration (including invasive species management), including fish stocking programs to support existing populations or reintroduce functionally extinct populations, or restore habitats (artificial reefs)
	Marine protected areas to protect habitat (certain fishing techniques allowed)
	Food web management to regulate trophic interactions
	Actions to reduce/prevent input of nutrients and/or silt into water bodies

For aquaculture, the measure groups are primarily directed towards nutrients, NIS, or benthic habitats in line with the sectors agreed in section 2.2.1.

Table 4-2 Preliminary list of groups of measures for aquaculture.

Groups of measures	Measures
Planning, regulations and licensing procedures to operate	Periodic inspections by competent authorities to verify compliance of aquaculture facilities and their operation
	Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) on single projects or in combination with other projects
	Aquaculture zoning and site selection using an ecosystem-based approach
	Promote and adopt hydrodynamic and ecological modelling for predicting areas of potential impact, nutrient dispersion, solid deposition, and carrying capacity of the receiving environment
Monitoring and reporting	Carry out monitoring activities based on national legislation or other type of authorisation given by competent authorities
	Monitor aquaculture facilities regularly using on site- and facility-specific requirements
	Assess the quality of water, sediment, and the condition of bottom habitats and species at regular intervals and, where practicable, continuously or automatically
	Record and make data (e.g. feeding, nutrient losses, mortality, waste collection, veterinary medicines, antifouling etc.) available to competent authorities and in a format that is comparable with other national monitoring programmes or regulations
Manage nutrient and organic enrichment	Manage nutrient discharges at farm level to avoid cumulative impacts
	Assess farm impacts on benthic habitats with environmental monitoring tools
	Promote the adoption of models to evaluate the assimilative capacity of the environment
	Improve fish feed and feeding practices
	Adopt site-appropriate wastewater treatment technologies
	Adopt best practices to manage biowastes
Prevent interactions with wild fauna	Implement measures and redundant risk management strategies to prevent escapees
	Implement measures to prevent lethal incidents with wild fauna
Reduce risks from the use of non-indigenous species (NIS)	Perform risk assessments for introduction of NIS for aquaculture purposes (and associated species)
	Select and use locally absent species under documented conditions
	Implement biofouling management plans
Sustainable use of living resources	Improve feeding strategies and practices
	Promote alternative diets and environmentally friendly feeds

Groups of measures	Measures
Reduce pollution by hazardous substances	Promote biosecurity and preventive health management (e.g. vaccination) strategies
	Adopt good animal welfare practices and develop robust species-specific operational welfare indicators (OWI)
	Reduce pharmaceutical use, which may damage the environment and increase antimicrobial resistance
	Promote early warnings and communication systems among farms to manage disease outbreak and treatments
	Promote responsible use of biocides and biocide-free antifouling strategies
Minimize marine Litter	Implement appropriate practices and technologies to prevent plastic waste
	Design equipment and materials with the least environmental impact
Noise reduction	Avoid or minimize harm to marine life due to acoustic disturbance and noise pollution from aquaculture operations

5 Concluding remarks

The European Green Deal (EGD) acknowledges that EU fisheries have yet to achieve sustainability by introducing the [Action Plan to protect and restore marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries](#) under the [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#). The Action Plan calls for Member States to intensify efforts to meet their existing obligations under current EU law and policy, such as GES under the MSFD. Reducing the risk of overexploitation is a clear overall objective and calls for defining clear operational management objectives and targets to support the shift towards responsible aquaculture and fisheries with low impact on the environment, and the restoration of biodiversity. The newly adopted [Nature Restoration Regulation](#) (NRR) aims to support these objectives by mandating restoration targets for specified habitats and species, including measures that should cover at least 20% of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030.

A key component of this report is the introduction of a semi-quantitative assessment framework designed to evaluate the impacts of different fisheries and aquaculture activities on marine ecosystems at regional level. This approach links specific human pressures to key ecosystem components, allowing for a nuanced understanding of how different activities affect marine biodiversity, habitat quality, and overall ecosystem health. By categorising fisheries and aquaculture activities into relevant sectors and assessing their direct pressures, this framework provides essential insights into the drivers of environmental impacts and identifies areas where management actions may be most effective.

The HELCOM Sufficiency of Measures (SoM) analysis, presented in this report, represents a structured, preliminary step towards evaluating the effectiveness of current measures in managing the environmental pressures from fisheries and aquaculture. This framework, when combined with the insights from collaborative networks like the European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET), can help guide policy adjustments and identify areas where intensified or additional actions are required to meet sustainability objectives across Europe's seas.

Further, the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) aligns with these efforts by setting binding restoration targets, aiming to cover at least 20% of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030. Complementary measures, such as promoting area-based management, selective fishing gear, and ecosystem-friendly aquaculture practices, provide critical pathways for reducing the risk of overexploitation, minimising habitat degradation, and fostering the resilience of marine ecosystems.

5.1 Where we are now

The analysis presented in this report represents a first attempt to comprehensively evaluate the environmental impacts of different fisheries and aquaculture subsectors within Europe's seas. This detailed categorisation allows for a more nuanced understanding of how different practices affect marine ecosystems, setting a new standard for the scale and depth of such assessments.

The novelty of this approach lies in its granular analysis, which offers a level of detail that has not been previously achieved in EU-wide evaluations of fisheries and aquaculture. By breaking down the activities into categories with specific characteristics, we can better capture the varied effects of each subsector on marine habitats, species, and overall ecosystem health.

This assessment is intended as a starting point in an iterative process. It will evolve and improve over time as new data becomes available and our understanding of marine ecosystems deepens. Future iterations will benefit from a growing knowledge base, incorporating the latest research and findings on

environmental impacts. Additionally, a higher spatial resolution will enable us to identify and analyse regional variations more accurately, providing a clearer picture of localised impacts across EU waters. In this context, the ongoing EEA study on mapping small-scale fishing effort will provide valuable input, enabling a more detailed examination of this important segment of the fishing fleet.

As our data and methodologies improve, this evolving framework can serve as a useful tool for guiding sustainable practices in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors. By continually refining our assessment, we aim to support the EU's broader environmental and sustainability goals, ensuring that the marine environment remains resilient and productive.

5.2 Where we are heading

To continue supporting and assessing progress on the transition to sustainable fisheries and a responsible aquaculture sector, future developments will explore regional and subregional specificities, opportunities, solutions and trade-offs of different scenarios. This will include:

- **A more advanced methodology for spatial analysis** to accurately describe the spatial dimensions and overlaps between various pressures on marine environments. This should help to quantify the magnitude of each pressure's effect on different ecosystem components, following established methodologies, such as those proposed by Korpinen et al. (2021).
- **A revised Impact scoring** that considers recent progress in environmental assessments, such as those derived from the latest Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) evaluations and insights from Common Implementation Strategy (CIS) Task Groups. These revisions will ensure that impact scores reflect the most current understanding of human activities on marine ecosystems.
- **Improved coverage and spatial resolution** to capture subregional variations that align with other EU marine directives, namely the MSFD. This higher-resolution approach will enable a more precise identification of subregional differences in pressures and impacts. Additionally, expanding the scope of assessments to cover other marine regions, including the Baltic Sea and the Black Sea, enhances the comprehensiveness of the analysis, allowing for a more holistic understanding of impacts across Europe's marine environment.
- **Incorporating Uncertainty and Confidence Scores** to improve the robustness of the scoring mechanism associated with each assessment. This will allow users to better understand the reliability of the data and the degree of confidence in the results, making the assessments more transparent and useful for decision-making processes. Confidence scoring will also help identify areas where further research or data collection is most needed to reduce uncertainties.

In addition, a critical element remains in addressing one of the principal goals of MSFD, i.e., to implement measures, where needed, to maintain or achieve GES. For this, Member States report Programmes of Measures (PoM) under MSFD Art. 13. However, the current lack of measurable metrics to assess the progress and outcomes hinders the ability to determine whether the implemented or proposed measures effectively contribute to achieving their objectives. Establishing quantifiable links between measures and specific targets is essential to track progress on GES, the effectiveness of measures and to make necessary adjustments to achieve the overarching goals of the MSFD. To support this effort, we intend to further explore methodologies such as HELCOM's Sufficiency of Measures (SoM) analysis and JRC's [Blue2](#) framework, to evaluate the effectiveness of measures aimed at improving the environmental status of Europe's marine regions.

6 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy	
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment	
EC	European Commission	
EU	European Union	
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations	
GES	Good Environmental Status	
GFCM	General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean	
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea	www.ices.dk
ISPRA	Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale	www.isprambiente.gov.it
MSY	Maximum Sustainable Yield	
NIS	Non-indigenous species	
TAC	Total Allowable Catch	
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem	
WOAH	World Organisation for Animal Health	

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Annex 1. Linkage framework for fisheries and aquaculture

Table A1.1 Fisheries_stage 1: Sector-Pressure linkages (see a short description of pressures below)

Sector / Human Activities	Type	Physical damage		Other physical disturbance		Contamination by hazardous substances	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Biological disturbance	
	Pressure	Siltation/ Smothering	Abrasion	Noise	Marine Litter	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Introduction of non-indigenous species (NIS)	Species Extraction
Passive pelagic	passive gear (driftnets, drifting longlines, etc.)		x	x	x	x			x
Passive demersal	passive gear (pots, traps, handlines, etc.)		x	x	x	x			x
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	vessels < 12m using pelagic trawls		x	x	x	x			x
Small vessels - active demersal	vessels < 12m using active bottom contacting gear (bottom trawling, dredges, etc.)	x	x	x	x	x			x
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	vessels >12m using pelagic trawls		x	x	x	x		x	x
Large vessels - active demersal	vessels >12m using active bottom contacting gear (bottom trawling, dredges, etc.)	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	vessels > 40m targeting forage fish species			x	x	x		x	x

Table A1.2 Fisheries_stage 1: Sector-Ecological characteristic linkages (see short descriptions below)

Type	Pressure	Ecological Characteristic									
		Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	Marine Mammals	Fish	Elasmobranchs	Reptiles	Seabirds	Cephalopods	Food Web (D4)
Physical damage	Siltation/ Smothering	X	X			X	X			X	X
	Abrasion	X	X			X	X			X	X
Other physical disturbance	Noise			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Marine Litter	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Contamination by hazardous substances	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Nutrient and organic enrichment	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Biological disturbance	Invasive species	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Species Extraction	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table A1.3 Aquaculture_stage 1: Sector-Pressure linkages (see a short description of sectors and pressures below)

Sector / Human Activities	Physical Loss	Physical damage			Other physical disturbance		Contamination by hazardous substances	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Biological disturbance		
	Substrate Loss	Siltation/ Smothering	Abrasion	Selective extraction of <u>non-living resources</u> from the seabed and subsoil	Noise	Marine Litter	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Introduction of non-indigenous species (NIS)	Species Extraction	Interaction with wild organisms
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	X
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	X	X			X	X	X	X		X	X
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)						X	X	X	X	X	X
High trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)										X	
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	X	X			X	X		X	X	X	
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	X		X		X	X		X	X	X	
Low trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)											
Polyculture sea-based coastal	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Polyculture sea-based offshore	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Algae sea-based	X	X			X	X			X		

Table A1.4 Aquaculture_stage 1: Pressure-Ecological characteristic linkages (see short descriptions below)

Type	Pressure	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	Marine Mammals	Fish	Reptiles	Seabirds	Cephalopods	Food Web (D4)
Physical Loss	Substrate Loss	X							
Physical damage	Siltation/ Smothering	X							
	Abrasion	X	X						
	Selective extraction of non-living resources from the seabed and subsoil								
Other physical disturbance	Noise	X		X	X	X	X	X	
	Marine Litter	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Contamination by hazardous substances	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	X							
Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Nutrient and organic enrichment	X	X		X				
Biological disturbance	Invasive species	X	X		X				
	Species Extraction		X		X				X
	Interaction with wild organisms	X		X	X	X	X		

Table A1.5 Risk Assessment for fisheries in the Northeast Atlantic region (stage 2)

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	A	0.03
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Fish	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Elasmobranchs	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Cephalopods	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Food Web (D4)	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	A	0.03
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Fish	WP	P	L	0.0335
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Elasmobranchs	WP	P	L	0.0335
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Cephalopods	WP	P	L	0.0335
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/ Smothering	Food Web (D4)	WP	P	C	0.134
passive demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	A	0.03
passive demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Abrasion	Fish	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Abrasion	Elasmobranchs	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Abrasion	Cephalopods	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Abrasion	Food Web (D4)	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	A	0.03
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Fish	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Elasmobranchs	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Cephalopods	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Food Web (D4)	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	R	A	0.0024
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	A	0.03
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Fish	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Elasmobranchs	WP	P	L	0.0335
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Cephalopods	WP	P	L	0.0335
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Food Web (D4)	WP	P	C	0.134
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Marine Mammals	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Fish	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Elasmobranchs	L	C	L	0.01106

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Reptiles	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Seabirds	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Cephalopods	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Food Web (D4)	L	C	L	0.01106
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Marine Mammals	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Fish	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Elasmobranchs	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Reptiles	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Seabirds	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Cephalopods	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Food Web (D4)	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Marine Mammals	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Fish	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Elasmobranchs	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Reptiles	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Seabirds	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Cephalopods	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Food Web (D4)	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Marine Mammals	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Fish	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Elasmobranchs	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Reptiles	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Seabirds	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Cephalopods	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Food Web (D4)	L	P	C	0.066
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Marine Mammals	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Reptiles	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Seabirds	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Food Web (D4)	L	O	L	0.005445
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	L	R	L	0.00132

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Fish	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	R	L	0.00132
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	L	R	L	0.00132
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Fish	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Reptiles	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Seabirds	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Fish	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Reptiles	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Seabirds	WP	R	L	0.00268

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	WP	R	L	0.00268
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Fish	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Reptiles	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Seabirds	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Fish	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Reptiles	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Seabirds	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Fish	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Reptiles	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Seabirds	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	WP	R	L	0.00268
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Food Web (D4)	WP	R	L	0.00268
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	P	C	0.066
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	P	A	0.67
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	P	C	0.066
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	P	C	0.006

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Seabirds	L	P	C	0.066
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	S	P	L	0.0015
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	L	P	C	0.066
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	O	C	0.00198
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	L	P	C	0.066
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	P	A	0.67
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	P	C	0.066
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	P	C	0.006
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Seabirds	L	P	L	0.0165
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	S	P	A	0.03
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	S	P	L	0.0015
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	P	A	0.67
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	WP	P	C	0.134
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	P	L	0.0015
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Seabirds	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	O	A	0.0099
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	L	P	C	0.066
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	O	A	0.1089
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	P	A	0.67
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	P	A	0.33
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	O	A	0.0099
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	L	P	A	0.33
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	L	0.0015
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	S	P	L	0.0015
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	P	L	0.0165
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	P	A	0.67
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	P	L	0.0015

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Seabirds	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	S	P	L	0.0015
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	P	A	0.03
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	E	P	C	0.002
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	S	P	C	0.006
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	P	A	0.67
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	S	P	C	0.006
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	P	L	0.0015
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Seabirds	WP	P	L	0.0335
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	O	C	0.04422
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	O	A	0.2211
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	O	A	0.2211

Table A1.6 Risk Assessment for fisheries in the Mediterranean region (stage 2)

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Small vessels - active demersal	Siltation/Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - active demersal	Siltation/Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	WP	C	C	0.08978
passive pelagic	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
passive demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
passive demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Abrasion	Fish	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Abrasion	Elasmobranchs	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Abrasion	Cephalopods	L	C	C	0.04422
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	L	C	C	0.04422
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Fish	L	C	C	0.04422
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Elasmobranchs	L	C	C	0.04422
Small vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Cephalopods	L	C	C	0.04422
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	WP	P	A	0.67
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Fish	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Elasmobranchs	WP	P	C	0.134
Large vessels - active demersal	Abrasion	Cephalopods	WP	P	C	0.134
passive pelagic	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
passive pelagic	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
passive pelagic	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
passive pelagic	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	L	0.001005
passive pelagic	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
passive pelagic	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
passive demersal	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
passive demersal	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
passive demersal	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
passive demersal	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	L	0.001005
passive demersal	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
passive demersal	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Small vessels - active demersal	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Fish	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - active demersal	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	C	0.00402
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Elasmobranchs	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	L	O	C	0.02178
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	A	0.1089
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	A	0.1089
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	A	0.1089
passive pelagic	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	L	O	C	0.02178

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	C	0.02178
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
passive demersal	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - active demersal	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	O	C	0.00198
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Elasmobranchs	L	O	L	0.005445
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	C	0.02178
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	C	A	0.0201
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	S	O	A	0.0099
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Fish	L	C	C	0.04422
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	C	C	0.04422
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	O	A	0.0099
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Seabirds	S	O	A	0.0099
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	L	C	C	0.04422
passive pelagic	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Fish	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	L	C	C	0.04422
passive demersal	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	L	C	C	0.04422
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	A	0.4489
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	S	R	A	0.0024
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	C	A	0.4489
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	C	A	0.2211
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	R	A	0.0024
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	WP	C	A	0.4489
Small vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMes	S	R	A	0.0024
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMes	WP	C	A	0.4489
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	C	0.02178
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	R	A	0.0264

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Fish	L	C	A	0.2211
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	L	C	A	0.2211
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	R	A	0.0024
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	WP	C	A	0.4489
Small vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	L	R	A	0.0264
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Reptiles	L	R	A	0.0264
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Seabirds	L	R	L	0.00132
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - pelagic trawlers	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	S	R	A	0.0024
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	R	A	0.0024
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - active demersal	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	S	C	L	0.001005
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	A	0.4489
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Marine Mammals	S	C	A	0.0201
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Fish	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Elasmobranchs	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Reptiles	S	R	A	0.0024
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Cephalopods	WP	C	C	0.08978
Large vessels - reduction fisheries	Species Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978

Table A1.7 Risk Assessment for aquaculture in the Northeast Atlantic region (stage 2)

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	C	C	0.00402
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Fish	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Reptiles	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Seabirds	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Cephalopods	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Fish	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Reptiles	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Seabirds	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Cephalopods	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Noise	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Algae sea-based	Noise	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	P	L	0.0015

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
Algae sea-based	Noise	Fish	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Noise	Reptiles	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Noise	Seabirds	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Noise	Cephalopods	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	O	L	0.005445
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	O	A	0.1089
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	O	A	0.1089
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	O	L	0.005445
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Marine Litter	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Marine Litter	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Marine Litter	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	E	P	C	0.002
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	E	P	C	0.002
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Fish	E	P	C	0.002
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Invasive species	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	C	0.01072
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Invasive species	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	C	0.01072
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Invasive species	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	C	0.01072
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Invasive species	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	C	0.01072
Algae sea-based	Invasive species	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	C	0.01072
Algae sea-based	Invasive species	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	R	C	0.01072
Algae sea-based	Invasive species	Fish	L	R	L	0.00132
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Living Resources Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Living Resources Extraction	Fish	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Living Resources Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Living Resources Extraction	Fish	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Living Resources Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	C	0.08978

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Living Resources Extraction	Fish	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)	Living Resources Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)	Living Resources Extraction	Fish	WP	C	C	0.08978
High trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	WP	C	C	0.08978
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Marine Mammals	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Fish	WP	P	C	0.134
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Fish	WP	P	C	0.134

Table A1.8 Risk Assessment for aquaculture in the Mediterranean region (stage 2)

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Substrate Loss	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Algae sea-based	Siltation/ Smothering	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Abrasion	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	C	C	0.00402
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Marine Mammals	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Reptiles	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Fish	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Noise	Cephalopods	S	C	L	0.001005
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	R	L	0.00132
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	R	L	0.00132
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Marine Mammals	L	R	L	0.00132
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Fish	L	R	L	0.00132
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Reptiles	L	R	L	0.00132
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Seabirds	L	R	L	0.00132
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Marine Litter	Cephalopods	L	R	L	0.00132
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	P	C	0.006
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Fish	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015

Sector	Pressure	Ecological.Characteristic	Overlap	Frequency	DoI	ImpactRisk
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Fish	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Invasive species	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	R	C	0.00528
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Invasive species	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	R	C	0.00528
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Invasive species	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	R	C	0.00528
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Invasive species	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	R	C	0.00528
Algae sea-based	Invasive species	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	R	C	0.00528
Algae sea-based	Invasive species	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	L	R	C	0.00528
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Living Resources Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Living Resources Extraction	Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	S	P	L	0.0015
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	Living Resources Extraction	Food Web (D4)	S	P	L	0.0015
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota)	L	O	L	0.005445
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	Interaction with wild organisms	Fish	L	O	L	0.005445
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	Interaction with wild organisms	Seabirds	S	C	L	0.001005

Short description pressures – fisheries

Type	Pressure	Short Description
Physical damage	Siltation/ Smothering	Smothering pressures relate to siltation or sedimentation on the surface of the seabed. Activities associated with this pressure type include marine and coastal construction, aquaculture, land claim/reclamation, navigation dredging, disposal at sea, marine mineral extraction, fishing, cable and pipeline laying, and various construction activities.
	Abrasion	Abrasion pressures relate to disturbance of the substrate at or below the surface of the seabed. Abrasion pressure is associated with bottom-contacting mobile and set fishing activities, in particular otter trawling, dredging for shellfish, and navigation and beam trawling. Other activities with a limited spatial footprint also cause abrasion.
Other physical disturbance	Noise	Ocean noise refers to sounds made by human activities that can temporarily or permanently interfere with, or impair the ability of marine animals to hear natural sounds in the ocean. Noise may also cause physiological or behavioural effects. Human activities that cause ocean noise include marine traffic (shipping), recreational boating, fishing vessels, energy exploration, military sonar, and inshore and offshore infrastructures (construction and operations).
	Marine Litter	Marine litter is any persistent, manufactured, or processed solid material that is discarded, disposed of, or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. Marine litter consists of items that have been made or used by people and deliberately discarded or unintentionally lost into the sea and on beaches, including such materials transported into the marine environment from land by rivers, draining, or sewage systems, or by winds. For example, marine litter consists of: plastics, wood, metals, glass, rubber, clothing, paper, etc. Land-based sources of marine litter include tourism, sewage, and illegal or poorly managed landfills. Sea-based sources include shipping and fishing.
Contamination by hazardous substances	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	Examples of this pressure include discharges from ships, hydrocarbon exploration and production, atmospheric deposition, and riverine inputs. Compounds of concern include: For marine sediments, the main transition elements and compounds of concern include arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, mercury, nickel, lead, and zinc. Organometallic compounds such as tributyltin (TBT) and its derivatives can be highly persistent, and even low levels of exposure can cause chronic toxicity. Hydrocarbons, including polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH). Priority substances listed in Annex II of Directive 2008/105/EC[1]. Synthetic compounds, including pesticides, antifoulants, and pharmaceuticals.
Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Increased levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, silicon and iron in the marine environment compared to background concentrations. Anthropogenic sources include waste water, terrestrial/agricultural runoff, sewage discharges, aquaculture, and atmospheric deposition. Nutrient enrichment may lead to eutrophication (see also organic enrichment).
Biological disturbance	Introduction of non-indigenous species (NIS)	The direct or indirect introduction of NIS, e.g., Chinese mitten crab <i>Eriocheir sinensis</i> , slipper limpet <i>Crepidula fornicata</i> , and Pacific oyster <i>Crassostrea gigas</i> and their subsequent spreading and out-competing of native species. Ballast water and hull

Type	Pressure	Short Description
		fouling can facilitate the spread of NIS. This pressure is also associated with aquaculture, translocation of organisms, and accidental releases.
	Species Extraction	The commercial exploitation of fish and shellfish stocks, including smaller-scale harvesting, recreational fishing, and scientific sampling. Ecological consequences include the sustainability of stocks, impacting energy flows through food webs, and the size and age composition within fish stocks. This pressure includes bycatch associated with fishing activities.

Short description – ecological component - fisheries and aquaculture

Ecological Characteristic	Short Description
Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): VMEs	The ecological or environmental area of the seabed, inhabited by one or more living species. This ecosystem component also includes all benthos - those flora and fauna found on the bottom or in the bottom sediments of the sea not listed separately above.
Benthic Habitat (& assoc. biota): non-VMEs	The ecological or environmental area of the seabed, inhabited by one or more living species. This ecosystem component also includes all benthos - those flora and fauna found on the bottom or in the bottom sediments of the sea not listed separately above.
Pelagic Habitats (& assoc. biota)	The ecological or environmental area of the water column, inhabited by one or more living species. The ecosystem component also includes plankton – small organisms that float or drift in great numbers in bodies of salt or freshwater. This includes zooplankton (including jellyfish) and phytoplankton but does not include the taxonomic groups listed separately above.
Marine Mammals	A mammal that lives in marine, or in some cases, an aquatic environment and obtains all or most of its food there.
Fish	Limbless, cold-blooded vertebrate animals with gills and fins living wholly in water. This includes both bony fish and elasmobranchs.
Elasmobranchs	Limbless, cold-blooded vertebrate animals with gills and fins living wholly in water. This includes both bony fish and elasmobranchs.
Reptiles	Cold-blooded, air-breathing vertebrates which have epidermal scales covering part or all of their body. Includes marine turtles.

Ecological Characteristic	Short Description
Seabirds	Birds that are adapted to life within the marine environment, spending most of their time at sea and sourcing all or most of their food from the marine environment.
Cephalopods	Any member of the class Cephalopoda, such as a squid, octopus, cuttlefish, or nautilus, characterised by bilateral body symmetry, a prominent head, and a set of arms or tentacles.
Food Web (D4)	All elements of the marine food webs that should occur at normal abundance and diversity levels, ensuring the long-term abundance of species and retention of their full reproductive capacity.

Short description - aquaculture sectors

Human activities/sector	Short Description
High trophic species: sea-based coastal (pens)	Species (e.g., finfish, shrimps) whose farming is fully dependent on the use of external feeds or fertilisers.
High trophic species: sea-based offshore (pens)	
High trophic species: land-based open flow through (tanks)	
High trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)	
Low trophic species: sea-based long lines, raft	Species (e.g., bivalve shellfish) whose farming is entirely dependent on natural processes or on nutrients coming from other anthropogenic activity than the aquaculture farm; or fish species (e.g., mullets) whose farming is dependent on some supplementary feed or fertilisers in addition to the natural process.
Low trophic species: sea-based on the bottom	
Low trophic species: land-based RAS (tanks)	
Polyculture sea-based coastal	

Human activities/sector	Short Description
Polyculture sea-based offshore	It is a type of aquaculture that combines a single farm area with different aquatic species from various trophic levels, such as fish and extractive species.
Algae sea-based	Species of seaweeds whose farming is dependent entirely on natural processes.

Short description pressures – aquaculture

Physical Loss	Substrate Loss	This pressure type includes the permanent change of one marine habitat type to another through a change in substratum, including artificial substrates (e.g., concrete). In the case of aquaculture, the substrate loss is limited to the presence of concrete anchoring/mooring systems.
	Siltation/ Smothering	The smothering pressures of aquaculture relate to sedimentation on the surface of the seabed. Origin of pressures include uneaten food and organic and shell debris. In the case of algae farming, the pressure includes the shadowing effect.
Physical damage	Abrasion	Abrasion pressures relate to disturbance of the substrate at or below the surface of the seabed; aggregate and other mineral extraction is not covered by this pressure. Abrasion pressure is associated with bottom-contacting mobile and set fishing activities, in particular otter trawling, dredging for shellfish, and navigation and beam trawling. Other activities with a limited spatial footprint also cause abrasion.
	Selective extraction of <u>non-living resources</u> from the seabed and subsoil	This pressure relates to marine aggregate extraction and mining. Some removal of benthic organisms and alteration of seabed topography may also occur.
Other physical disturbance	Noise	Ocean noise refers to sounds made by human activities that can temporarily or permanently interfere with, or impair the ability of marine animals to hear natural sounds in the ocean. Noise may also cause physiological or behavioural effects. Aquaculture activities that cause ocean noise are limited to the use of vessels for routine operations and installation/maintenance of facilities.
	Marine Litter	Marine litter is any persistent, manufactured, or processed solid material that is discarded, disposed of, or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. Marine litter consists of items that have been made or used by people and deliberately discarded or unintentionally lost into the sea and on beaches, including such materials transported into the marine environment from land by rivers, draining, or sewage systems, or by winds. Structures and materials used for aquaculture

		activities (e.g. nets, ropes, floats and buoys, strapping material, mash bags, lantern nets, trays, and moorings) may impact marine fauna, contribute to microplastic pollution, coastal degradation and interfere with other sea uses (e.g., tourism).
Contamination by hazardous substances	Introduction of Contaminating compounds	This pressure can be associated to farming activities (e.g., disinfectants, antifoulants, and pharmaceuticals).
Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Nutrient and organic enrichment	Aquaculture can lead to increased levels of nitrogen and phosphorus in the marine environment compared to background concentrations. Nutrient enrichment may lead to eutrophication (see also organic enrichment). This pressure is mainly associated with the farming of high trophic species in intensive aquaculture and the release of nitrogen and phosphorus-based compounds and organic matter through the release of waste, such as undigested feed, metabolic excretion products and faeces.
Biological disturbance	Introduction of non-indigenous species (NIS)	The introduction of NIS in the marine environment can exert pressures, mainly through i) predation on native species, ii) competition for food resources and space and alterations to habitat complexity. The introduction of non-target species, mainly associated with bivalve shellfish introduction, may affect cultivated/wild spats of commercial species, the quality of the environment (e.g., potentially toxic phytoplanktonic species) and the biodiversity.
	Species Extraction	This pressure also includes harvesting of stocks (e.g., small-pelagic fish) for the production of fish meal and fish oil for aquaculture feeds. In the case of bivalve shellfish farming, the pressure regards the extraction of phytoplankton above the carrying capacity of the system. Ecological consequences include the sustainability of stocks, impacting energy flows through food webs, and the size and age composition within fish stocks.
	Interaction with wild organisms	Interactions related to escapees; transfer/spread of pathogens; incidents with wild fauna (fish, birds, marine mammals, reptiles).

Annex 2. Files for reporting implemented measures for fishing and aquaculture

The questionnaire to be distributed to the European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) and other expert groups is shown here. It has been tailored to allow the reporting of measures on fisheries and aquaculture of EU Member States.

1. Notes

Collation of information on existing national, regional and global measures/actions for managing fisheries and aquaculture.

Existing measures will be linked to the SOM measure types (generalised measures) and used as a basis for evaluating the effect of existing measures.

2. General Instructions

DATABASE FOR MEASURES OF EXISTING POLICIES FOR SOM ANALYSIS

Instructions on the content of the database

National measures list preparer(s)
Name(s):
Organization(s):
Contact information(s):

Policy Framework

A. Name of policy framework - filling name of policy framework.

The name of the policy framework that contains the listed measure. For national policies - only such frameworks/measures should be included separately in the database which are not related to any listed multinational policy frameworks (to avoid overlap of measures included in the database). For instance, the new measures of MSFD PoMs or purely national frameworks/measures are included separately. Those national measures related to the listed multinational policy frameworks are considered and can be specified when assessing the national implementation status of the respective multinational framework (see Columns N-AE).

B. Scale of policy framework.

Categories:

Global

EU

Regional: HELCOM, OSPAR, Barcelona Convention, others

National

Local

C. Country

For National and Local policies in Column B - fill in the country abbreviation (options are specified).

Measures

D. Name of a measure.

Provide a short name of a measure reflecting its substance.

E. Description of a measure.

Provide a description of a measure allowing one to understand its content, e.g., what needs to be done and by whom, whether there is an enforcement mechanism, specific conditions of application (e.g., if a measure applies to specific areas/substances/items, if specific activities are exempted from measure's implementation). Where relevant, include here also specification on the spatial or temporal extent of application of a measure and planned financial investment.

F. Type of a measure.

NOTE! Only types of measures with concrete effects are included in the database.

Categories:

Administrative. Including controlling measures, and regulatory measures (e.g., setting emission standards, bans). **NOT** including measures related to monitoring, coordination, developing indicators, and setting targets.

Economic instrument.

Technical measure.

Information and awareness-raising measures. NOT including measures related to building knowledge and information base, information systems/tools.

Various measures. When various types of measures are joined under one measure in the database (like a set of measures/instruments), and cannot be specified now.

National measures. When specific measures to be implemented will be set nationally (the international framework prescribes only general requirements/measures), and cannot be specified now.

Not known yet. Exact measures to be taken are not known yet. But it will be set in the near future (and implementation could be expected in the BAU timeframe).

Measure characteristics

G. Addressed Activity.

Specify Activity(ies) addressed by a measure. List of activities according to MSFD Annex III, and slightly modified for the purposes of SOM. More than one activity can be identified for each measure (requires macros to be enabled). The activity list is included at the end of these instructions. Please familiarize yourself with the list before answering this question.

NOTE! There can be measures which address the pressure or the state directly (e.g., litter removal, habitat restoration). Then, specify the pressure/state component which is targeted by a measure.

H. NOTES

Clarify "Other" responses to Addressed Activity. Also used to indicate species targeted by the measure for biodiversity elements (marine mammals, birds, fish) and waste item types targeted for marine litter.

I. Addressed Pressure. (Options are specified)

J. KTM (Optional; Options are specified)

K. Measure-Pressure time-lag.

Specify the time-lag in the effect of a measure on pressures after its full implementation (after it is put in place). If there is no time-lag, filling "No".

NOTE! Filled based on the assessment of environmental experts.

Provide the best estimate of time-lag. Suggested answers are provided, but more specific answers are accepted. The primary purpose is to determine if time-lag extends the effect of implemented measures across the base year threshold (i.e., a measure fully implemented in mid-2014 but with an estimated 2-year time-lag has effects that extend beyond 1.1.2016 (the threshold for new vs old measures))

L. Legal status of a measure.

Categories:

Mandatory

Agreed

Voluntary

Implementation status

M. Grouping based on implementation status.

Filled by the task team

N-AE. Implementation status of a measure in countries.

Two columns are provided for each country. The **first column** has specified options for the implementation status of the measure.

NOTE! Implementation status is determined for the date of (TBD)

Categories:

1. Fully implemented
2. Not yet (fully) implemented
3. Uncertain (There are reasons for uncertainty in measure's implementation, thus its implementation in the BAU timeframe cannot be assumed)
4. Other (e.g., not party to the listed international policy framework)

The **second column** provides space to:

- provide details about national measure(s) used to comply with the listed multinational framework (International conventions, EU directives, RSC recommendations, etc.)

- explain responses of "Uncertain" or "Other" to the implementation status question
- providing any other additional information

AF. Will it change the pressure in BAU?

Filled by the task team

AG. Effectiveness of measures data

If measure effectiveness data is available, provide a link or citation to the source. The data itself is not requested.

Please familiarise yourself with the activity list below before answering the "Addressed activity" question (column G).

Aquaculture:

Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure

Marine plant harvesting

Commercial fishing:

Fish and shellfish harvesting (bottom-touching towed gears, professional/commercial)

Fish and shellfish harvesting (pelagic towed gears, stationary gears, professional/commercial)

Fish and shellfish processing

Direct to pressure or state component

Other: ...

Various: ...

European Topic Centre on
Biodiversity and ecosystems

<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-be>

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